

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D5.1

Critical assessment and key recommendations for
Interregional financing

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.1 presents an in-depth analysis of the Smart Specialisation Strategy priorities of key European regions and their alignment with EU Mission Ocean’s objectives. Further, it analyses what the most promising areas for further action in support of Mission Ocean are and how these can be pursued. The report also presents EU-level initiatives and funding opportunities for interregional collaboration, supporting regions interested in innovating their blue policies in understanding how to make use of existing opportunities and ground them in their regional policymaking. It analyses, compares and benchmarks the funding mechanisms of selected regions in relation to blue growth/sustainable blue economy and innovation to identify innovative inner- and interregional funding and methods to accelerate reaching the objectives of Mission Ocean by 2030. The report also lists promising EU funding and support mechanisms for regions and provides examples of how to use the new ERDF Interregional Innovation Instrument (I3) to support regions in accelerating market uptake of pilots and demonstrations in support of Mission Ocean’s objectives. Finally, the report presents case studies to illustrate successful interregional collaboration opportunities and inspire further collaboration between regional stakeholders.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and in this deliverable

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
ADMA Energy	Advanced Manufacturing for Energy applications in harsh environments (it is the name of an existing TSSP)
CHOIR	Challenge-Oriented Interregional Innovation Partnership
CHOIR	Challenge-Oriented Innovation Partnership
EC	European Commission
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
EU	European Union
I3 Instrument	Interregional Innovation Investment Instrument
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MRE	Marine Renewable Energy (it is the name of an existing TSSP)
ORE	Offshore Renewable Energy
P4B	PREP4BLUE
Quadruple Helix	The Quadruple Helix innovation model includes stakeholders and actors from the public sector, industry, academia, and citizens
PRI	Partnerships for Regional Innovation
RIV	Regional Innovation Valleys
S3 (or RIS3)	Smart Specialisation Strategy (the same as RIS3 - Research and Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategy)
S4 (or RIS4)	Sustainable Smart Specialisation Strategies (the same as RIS4 - Research and Innovation Sustainable Smart Specialisation Strategy)
S5 (or RIS5)	Sustainable and Social Smart Specialisation Strategies (the same as RIS5 - Research and Innovation Sustainable and Social Smart Specialisation Strategy)
SBE Platform	Sustainable Blue Economy Platform (not to be confounded with SBEP, Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership)
TSSP	Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnership (also called S3 or RIS3 Partnership)
Mission (Ocean)	EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters
SBE	Sustainable Blue Economy
DOKA	Eastern Black Sea Development Agency
R&I	Research and Innovation
EDP	Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/edp)
EIE	European Innovation Ecosystems

Overview of regions analysed in the report and their respective countries

Table 2. List of regions analysed in the document with hyperlinks to their respective S3 where available.

Country	Region
Austria (AT)	Ostösterreich and Wien
Belgium (BE)	Flanders
Bulgaria (BG)	South-Western and South-Central Bulgaria
Czech Republic (CZ)	Liberec, Olomouc, South Moravia
Denmark (DK)	Capital Region of Denmark, South Denmark
Estonia (EE)¹	
Finland (FI)	Helsinki-Uusimaa , Kainuu, Kymenlaakso , Ostrobothnia, Oulu , Southwest Finland , South Savo, North Savo
France (FR)	Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, Brittany , Grand Est, Guadeloupe, Hauts-de-France, La Réunion , Occitania , Pays de la Loire , Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur
Germany (DE)	Bayern, Berlin, Bremen , Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Rhineland, Schleswig-Holstein
Greece (GR)	Crete , Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, Western Greece
Hungary (HU)	Közep-Magyarorszög
Italy (IT)	Aosta Valley, Emilia-Romagna , Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Lazio , Liguria, Lombardy, Piedmont, Puglia , Sicily , Tuscany
Latvia (LV)²	
Malta (MT)	Gozo-Malta
Moldova (MD)³	
Netherlands (NL)	East Netherlands, North Netherlands , West Netherlands
Norway (NO)	Sogn and Fjordane
Poland (PL)	Małopolska, Pomorskie
Portugal (PT)	Azores , Centro, Lisboa e Vale do Tejo , Madeira , Norte
Romania (RO)	București-Ilfov, North East Romania, North West Romania, South-East Romania
Slovenia (SI)	Western Slovenia
Spain (ES)	Andalucia, Asturias, Basque Community, Canary Islands, Cantabria, Catalonia, Castilla Y Leon, Galicia , Murcia , Navarra, Valencia
Sweden (SE)	Blekinge , Dalarna, Skåne, Stockholm, Västra Götaland
Turkey (TR)	Çucurova, DOKA – Eastern Black Sea Development Agency
United Kingdom (UK)	Cornwall and Isles of Scilly, Scotland

¹ Estonia has been included in the analysis as a whole country due to its administrative structure.

² Latvia has been included in the analysis as a whole country due to its administrative structure.

³ Moldova has been included in the analysis as a whole country due to its administrative structure.

1 Introduction

The EU Mission ‘Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030’ (hereinafter referred to as Mission Ocean) aims „to provide a **systemic approach for the restoration of the ocean, seas and waters by 2030**“.⁴ In the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and The Committee of the Regions “EU Missions two years on assessment of progress and way forward”⁵, Mission Ocean is defined “as an inclusive, systemic and transformative initiative that bundles existing efforts at EU, national and regional levels”, contributing to „overcoming fragmented governance frameworks and supports key EU legislation and policies in marine, maritime and freshwater domains as well as related fields“. As such, Mission Ocean intends to act as a catalyst to streamline and bundle funding across government levels to reach its ambitious objectives. Through a pledging system, which allows relevant stakeholders to endorse its Charter⁶ and other instruments, Mission Ocean aims to connect activities and initiatives – and consequently funding – further to creating new opportunities by pulling together resources from different “EU, national and regional programmes, [...] pooling funds beyond R&I namely EMFAF national plans, BlueInvest with EUR 1.5 billion in risk finance, Recovery and Resilience Funds, Interreg and Copernicus”.⁷ Mission Ocean’s objective is to foster synergies with Member States to effectively and impactfully utilise funds under shared management. This includes aligning with regional and macro-regional Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3 or S3) and leveraging other regional strategic planning tools through the coordinated efforts of the Mission secretariats’ national hubs and other relevant national and regional implementation structures.⁸

This ambitious endeavour requires actors at all levels to be informed and collaborate on creating and exploiting regional, inter- and transregional opportunities, utilising regionally managed and other EU funds to support local priorities while contributing to Mission Ocean’s overall objectives (Table 3). One of the key instruments regions have to orient their action towards reaching Mission Ocean’s objectives are Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3 or RIS3) for research and innovation (R&I), which can be regarded as key drivers for strategic regional development. Deliverable 5.1 analyses S3 in relation to the three Mission objectives and respective sub-objectives (see Table 3 below), mapping the alignment between regional and EU-level priorities. Specifically, the deliverable focuses on RIS3 priorities related to the blue economy sector and see how they relate to the EU Mission Ocean’s objectives and cross-cutting enablers. It then analyses, compares and benchmarks the funding mechanisms of selected regions in relation to blue growth/sustainable blue economy and innovation to identify innovative inner- and interregional funding and methods to accelerate reaching the objectives of Mission Ocean by 2030. The report also lists promising EU funding and support mechanisms for regions and provide examples

⁴ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *EU Missions two years on: An assessment of progress in shaping the future we want and reporting on the review of Mission Areas and areas for institutionalised partnerships based on Articles 185 and 187 TFEU*, Commission Staff Working Document, SWD(2023) 260, 19 July 2023.

⁵ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *EU Missions two years on: assessment of progress and way forward*, Communication, COM(2023) 457, 19 July 2023.

⁶ European Commission, *Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Charter*, <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/MissionOceanWatersCharter>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Commission Staff Working Document, *EU Missions two years on: An assessment of progress in shaping the future we want and reporting on the review of Mission Areas and areas for institutionalised partnerships based on Articles 185 and 187 TFEU*, SWD(2023) 260, 19 July 2023.

⁸ European Commission, Directorate General Research and Innovation, *Implementation Plan*, Internal working document, 2021, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/d6162cbd-6d09-48fd-b5b4-d7d2be69972c_en?filename=ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_final.pdf. Accessed 27 November 2023.

of how to use the new ERDF Interregional Innovation Instrument (I3) to support regions in accelerating market uptake of pilots and demonstrations in support of Mission Ocean’s objectives.

Table 3. EU Mission Ocean objectives (2030) and sub-objectives for the different sea and freshwater basins and the Mission enablers.

Cross-cutting enablers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System • Public mobilisation and engagement 	Objective 1: Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protect a minimum of 30% of the EU’s sea area and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network • Strictly protect at least 10% of the EU’s sea area • Restore at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers • Contribute to relevant upcoming marine nature restoration targets including degraded seabed habitats and coastal ecosystems
	Objective 2: Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce by at least 50% plastic litter at sea • Reduce by at least 30% microplastics released into the environment • Reduce by at least 50% nutrient losses, the use and risk of chemical pesticides
	Objective 3: Make the sustainable blue economy carbon neutral and circular	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eliminate greenhouse gas emissions from maritime economic activities in the EU and sequester those emissions that cannot be avoided (net zero maritime emissions). • Develop zero-carbon and low-impact aquaculture, and promote circular, low carbon multi-purpose use of marine and water space

Connecting innovators in the different domains of sustainable blue economy across the European Union is crucial. Place-based innovation is key for Europe⁹, as grounding innovation in regional strategies ensures that innovators get the support they need in a favourable local ecosystem – and a clear policy support for priorities that are strategic for a given territory. S3 strategies are the instruments by which each region develops, illustrates, and guides innovation at its regional level, i.e., they are a proxy to define innovation in regional strategies and ecosystems.

Interregional financing builds on the idea of connecting regions that have similar and/or complementary ecosystems and strategies, and their quadruple-helix stakeholders. Interregional financing allows to mobilise greater amounts of financial resources than unilateral funding, and can thus help advance sustainable blue value chains.¹⁰ Geographical proximity is a driver for inter-regional

⁹ This concept is widely used in the literature and oral speeches (eg. Doussineau, M., Gnamus, A., Gomez Prieto, J., Haarich, S. and Holstein, F., *Smart Specialisation and Blue biotechnology in Europe*, EUR 30521 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020, ISBN 978-92-76-27753-8, doi:10.2760/19274, JRC122818) when speaking about local innovative ecosystems. To learn more about it, please read the following document: Mccann, P. and Soete, L., *Place-based innovation for sustainability*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020, ISBN 978-92-76-20392-6, doi:10.2760/250023, JRC121271.

¹⁰ We are using here a definition inspired by the how the Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument (I3) defines interregional cooperation. Read more here: European Commission, *Interregional Innovation Investments (I3)*, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/themes/research-innovation/interregional-innovation-investments_en. Accessed 12 November 2023.

collaboration, and has been widely discussed in literature.^{11 12} Interreg programmes¹³, sea basins and macro-regional strategies can build on and complement partnerships based on S3, either because two regions have similar S3 priorities and/or because of their geographical proximity. Sometimes these two axes overlap, as geographical neighbours can use interregional funding instruments to fund similar S3 priorities (e.g., through Interreg Baltic). This concept resonates with Mission Ocean's definition of associated regions, defined as areas that can benefit from the demonstration activities undertaken in EU-funded Mission projects (e.g., neighbouring regions and/or regions in a different sea basin) or that need to build capacity to plan the innovative solutions foreseen in regional pilots in the framework of HEU projects.¹⁴

This report will present the results from the mapping of S3 priorities aligned with Mission Ocean to then introduce relevant interregional funding tools based on innovation strategies, to favour a collaboration framework between regions that are not contiguously located. Interregional funding is an interesting tool to support the goals of Mission Ocean, as it reflects the need to ground research and innovation solutions contributing to the Mission objectives in the local and regional level (top-down)¹⁵. On the other hand, interregional financing and collaboration allow Mission-oriented projects to develop (bottom-up). Indeed, several regions are also currently implementing a Mission-oriented approach in their S3, with the objective to include "top-down" guiding policies/objectives in the entrepreneurial discovery process¹⁶ and develop S3 aligned with EU policy objectives. Interregional financing can spread this dynamic (bottom-up and top-down) to more regions:

- In the Mission, clear and precise objectives are set at the EU level with the goal of bringing everyone on board, including stakeholders and citizens who need to catch and feed the wave.
- For S3, each region can design and focus on its chosen priorities.
- Interregional collaboration and financing can be the necessary bridge between the top-down and bottom-up levels. Interregional collaboration and funding allow regions to work on common priorities to promote Mission Ocean's objectives, combining economic and market development of solutions and value chains.

Chapter 1 of this report analyses selected S3 strategies, with information collected through desk research, an online survey and interviews with regional authorities, to assess their relevance and

¹¹ For example in: Delecasse, É., *Politique de cohésion : la simplification à l'épreuve de la complexité d'Interreg*, Reflets et perspectives de la vie économique, vol. viii, no. 1, 2020, pp. 65-78.

¹² The basin approach is the one used in general when talking about cooperation in the SBE field. For example, the EU blue economy report 2022 dedicated its chapter 7.1 to a sea-basin analysis (European Commission, Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, Joint Research Centre, Addamo, A., Calvo Santos, A., Guillén, J. et al., *The EU blue economy report 2022*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/793264>. Accessed 12 November 2023.

¹³ For another reason, we will neither consider [Interreg Europe](https://www.interregeurope.eu/). It is indeed not a programme based on geographical proximity, but it is a policy-making instrument that does not direct funds to private for-profit companies. See <https://www.interregeurope.eu/apply-for-the-call#anchor-the-application-pack>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹⁴ See <https://errin.eu/events/concept-associated-regions-funding-associated-regions-under-mission-ocean-calls>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹⁵ More information about the rationale of Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 here (see page 23 for details about the scale-up phase): European Commission, Directorate General Research and Innovation, *Implementation Plan*, Internal working document, 2021, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/d6162cbd-6d09-48fd-b5b4-d7d2be69972c_en?filename=ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_final.pdf. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹⁶ European Commission, *Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP)*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/edp>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

alignment with Mission Ocean’s objectives and in which domains these have been addressed at the regional level.

Chapter 2 examines interregional funding and support mechanisms and assesses their relevance to regional stakeholders.

Chapter 3 provides examples of successfully funded interregional collaborations (case studies) that speak to the three Mission Objectives and propose a new framework of collaboration.

The document closes with **recommendations** and **conclusions** for regional stakeholders and stakeholders involved in Mission Ocean’s governance development.

2 Chapter 1: Mapping of RIS3 priorities aligned with the Mission Ocean and Waters objectives and their funding mechanisms

2.1 The RIS3 policy context for the current programming period 2021-2027

In 2010, the European Commission identified the need to use Regional Policy more efficiently to finance innovation in the most competitive sectors of each EU region, contributing to their smart growth. Regions would thus realise an assessment of their specific economic strengths and weaknesses through the elaboration of their regional Smart Specialisation Strategy (hereinafter referred to as S3 or RIS3 interchangeably).¹⁷ S3 are defined as “*national or regional innovation strategies which set priorities in order to build competitive advantage by developing and matching research and innovation own strengths to business needs in order to address emerging opportunities and market developments in a coherent manner, while avoiding duplication and fragmentation of efforts; a smart specialisation strategy may take the form of, or be included in, a national or regional research and innovation (R&I) strategic policy framework*”.¹⁸

As a consequence, in the 2014-2020 period, elaborating smart specialisation strategies became an ex-ante conditionality for regions to receive funding on research and innovation from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF).¹⁹ Proposals from regional stakeholders to finance innovation projects through the innovation component of the ERDF must be aligned with the S3 priorities, in order to be awarded.

Under the current programming period (2021-2027), projects funded under ERDF Policy Objective 1 (PO1) for a “more competitive and smarter Europe by promoting innovative and smart economic transformation and regional ICT connectivity” must be aligned with regional smart specialisation strategies.²⁰ In addition, a new thematic enabling condition for the good governance of national or regional smart specialisation strategies was introduced with seven fulfilment criteria as a prerequisite to access funding.²¹ Among the criteria¹² to fulfil this governance condition, the seventh is about

¹⁷ European Commission, *Regional Policy Contributing to smart growth in Europe 2020*, Communication, COM(2010) 553, 2010.

¹⁸ REGULATION (EU) No 1301/2013 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 17 December 2013 on the European Regional Development Fund and on specific provisions concerning the Investment for growth and jobs goal and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1080/2006.

¹⁹ Ibidem

²⁰ REGULATION (EU) 2021/1058 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 24 June 2021 on the European Regional Development Fund and on the Cohesion Fund.

²¹ REGULATION (EU) 2021/1060 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 24 June 2021 laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund Plus, the Cohesion Fund, the Just Transition Fund and the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund and financial rules for those and for the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, the Internal Security Fund and the Instrument for Financial Support for Border Management and Visa Policy. Annex IV – Criteria for the ERDF enabling condition 1.1: 1) Up-to-date analysis of challenges for innovation diffusion and digitalisation 2) Existence of competent regional and national institution or body, responsible for the management of the smart specialisation strategy 3) Monitoring and evaluation tools to measure performance towards the objectives of the strategy 4) Functioning of stakeholder co-operation (“entrepreneurial discovery process”) 5)

“measures for enhancing cooperation with partners outside a given Member State in priority areas supported by the S3”, speaking to interregional cooperation on shared S3 priorities. Developing an S3 therefore requires building a strong bottom-up process by engaging all the regional stakeholders in a constructive dialogue to identify a region’s most promising areas of specialisation. The S3 governance should thus create a favourable environment for the collaboration of quadruple helix stakeholders (including public authorities, industry, academia and citizens) around the topic of innovation.

Smart specialisation strategies are being increasingly connected with EU environmental objectives and notably the EU Green Deal. In fact, several regions have framed their S3 around transversal priorities or challenges to foster the green and digital transition.²² To this end, in the current programming period, some regions updated their S3 to include a strong environmental component, making them into so-called S4: Sustainable Smart Specialisation Strategy.²³ Some regions went even further by adding a social dimension to the sustainability component. This is the case, for example, of La Réunion, which, for 2021-2027, developed a Smart Specialisation Strategy for Social and Sustainable Development (so-called S5).²⁴

These examples illustrate clearly how the S3 framework has been pivotal to bringing the main areas of regional development under one umbrella, looking at all the main dimensions of regional development synergistically: economic, social, and environmental.

2.2 Methodology and objectives of this chapter

The methodology used to collect information on regional smart specialisation strategies consisted of a questionnaire (Annex 6.1) circulated among regional authorities, part of the network of the Prep4Blue partners [CPMR](#) and [s.Pro](#) (which manages the [SUBMARINER Network](#)), with the support of the S3 platform developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) to carry out research on regional priorities.²⁵ Between December 2022 and July 2023, 34 regions responded to the questionnaire, covering all the different Mission lighthouses, and representing a response rate of 46% (Figure 2).²⁶ The information gathered through the questionnaires was then complemented by a series of

Actions necessary to improve national or regional research and innovation systems, 6) Where relevant, actions to support industrial transition 7) Measures for enhancing cooperation with partners outside a given Member State in priority areas supported by the smart specialisation strategy

²² Miedzinski M., Coenen L., Larsen H., Matusiak M., Sarcina A., *Enhancing the sustainability dimension in Smart Specialisation strategies: a framework for reflection. Step-by-step reflection framework and lessons from policy practice to align Smart Specialisation with Sustainable Development Goals*, Miedzinski M., Matusiak M. editors, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, doi:10.2760/300268, JRC130497.

²³ That is the case for example for the region of Murcia (ES) and for the smart specialisation strategy of Serbia.

²⁴ Region Réunion, *De la S3 vers la “S5”: Stratégie de spécialisation intelligente pour un développement social & soutenable. Plan d’action pour la recherche et l’innovation 2022-2027*, https://regionreunion.com/IMG/pdf/plan_d_action_s5_21-27_vdef.pdf. Accessed 11 November 2023.

²⁵ Questionnaire sent to 74 regions from 23 EU and non-EU countries.

²⁶ FI (Helsinki-Uusimaa, Kymenlaakso, Oulu, Southwest Finland), FR (Brittany, Guadeloupe, Occitania, Pays de la Loire, La Réunion), DE (Bremen), GR (Crete, Western Greece, Eastern Macedonia and Thrace), IT (Emilia-Romagna, Lazio, Puglia, Sicily), MT (Gozo), Moldova, NL (North Netherlands), NO (Vestfold og Telemark), PL (Pomorskie), PT (Azores, Lisbon, Madeira, Norte), RO (Southeast Romania), ES (Galicia, Murcia, Valencia), SE (Blekinge, Västra Götaland), TR (Çucurova, DOKA – Eastern Black Sea Development Agency). Please note that in Moldova R&I priorities are elaborated at the national level. The national program for R&I transposes the principles of smart specialisation and identifies strategic R&I priorities, with several aligned with the objectives of the Mission. For this reason, in this report Moldova is discussed alongside regional entities despite being a national authority.

interviews with 26 regions²⁷ (Figure 2), offering concrete information on the implementation of their regional smart specialisation strategy, their governance structure and potential opportunities for interregional collaboration (the interview questionnaire can be found in Annex 6.2).

Figure 2. Overview of regions which responded to the online questionnaire developed by CPMR.

The regional smart specialisation strategies for the period 2021-2027 were analysed on the basis of the mission objectives, sub-objectives, and cross-cutting enablers. They were used as a guiding tool in

²⁷ FI (Oulu, Southwest Finland), FR (Guadeloupe, Occitanie, Pays de la Loire, La Réunion), GE (Bremen), GR (Crete, Western Greece), IT (Emilia-Romagna, Puglia, Sicily), MT (Gozo), NL (North Netherlands), PL (Pomorskie), PT (Azores, Lisbon, Madeira, Norte), RO (Southeast Romania), ES (Galicia, Murcia, Valencia), SE (Västra Götaland), TR (Çucurova, DOKA – Eastern Black Sea Development Agency)

the questionnaire and interviews to facilitate the identification of relevant S3 priorities by regional authorities that contribute to the achievement of these objectives.

Among the cross-cutting enablers, the digital ocean and water knowledge system has been retained for this study, being much more reflected in regional smart specialisation strategies than public mobilisation and engagement.

The study focuses on maritime regions, as many of them included S3 priorities related to the sustainable blue economy and thus aligned with the Mission objectives (Table 4). The appreciation of the alignment of S3 priorities with the Mission objectives has been firstly offered to regional authorities through the survey, used as an entry point to obtain a list of priorities corresponding to certain objectives of the Mission and with key information on interaction and support to the research and business community, and relevant funding models.

The interviews with regional stakeholders served to collect information on the context of the elaboration of the strategy and get a better understanding and confirmation of the connection between relevant S3 priorities and the Mission objectives.

Although the analysis is firstly based on priorities linked to the sustainable blue economy, other priority domains have been explored, such as water, environmental or agrifood-related priorities, due to their potential alignment with the Mission and notably the objective 2 on the reduction and prevention of pollution.

Our analysis also includes regions from non-EU countries, in particular from the Balkans and Black Sea region, in order to broaden the scope towards regions currently in a process of developing their smart specialisation strategy and/or investing in research and innovation for the development of a sustainable blue economy. Additionally, as the Danube and Black Sea lighthouse focuses on the preservation and restoration of freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, the study reflects the contribution received from Moldova, which established its National Programme for Research and Innovation transposing the principles of smart specialisation, with several priorities aligned with Mission objectives and the Danube and Black Sea lighthouse specific focus. Outermost regions from other EU sea basins, such as Guadeloupe and La Réunion, are also included. These regions host unique and particularly vulnerable coastal and marine ecosystems and are biodiversity hotspots.²⁸ Due to their important natural assets and efforts to develop innovation and research on marine conservation, they represent a strong added value for Mission Ocean, and their S3 priorities are reflected in this study.

²⁸ European Commission, *Europe's outermost regions*, https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/ocean/sea-basins/europes-outermost-regions_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

2.3 RIS3 2021-2027 Mapping: A good compass towards the achievement of the Mission Ocean and Waters objectives

Table 4. Overview of RIS3 regional mapping

- N° regions with **blue economy/blue growth/ maritime/sea domain: 16** (Azores (PT), Norte (PT), Madeira (PT), Pays de la Loire (FR), Gozo (MT), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Puglia (IT), Murcia (ES), Brittany (FR), Sicily (IT), La Réunion (FR), Occitania (FR), Lisboa (PT), Southwest Finland (FI), Pomorskie (PL), Lazio (IT))
- N° regions with **blue economy as a transversal topic: 5** (Galicia (ES), Crete (GR), Västra Götaland (SE), Blekinge (SE), Guadeloupe (FR))
- N° regions with **no blue economy area of specialisation or domain, but relevant S3 priorities in the sustainable blue economy and water sector: 8** (Oulu (FI), Western Greece (GR), North Netherlands (NL), Valencia (ES), Çucurova (TR), Bremen (DE), South-East Romania (RO), Kymenlaakso (FI)).

This first section presents the main results from the mapping of smart specialisation strategies in the different regions that responded to the questionnaire and were later interviewed. Specifically, this section presents the results from the S3 mapping to provide:

- A classification of S3 priorities according to Mission objectives, facilitating the identification of shared priorities among the regions studied and to boost the potential of interregional collaboration between the regions.
- An analysis of the main trends observed to identify opportunities and further explore the regional priorities in terms of R&I investments in line with the Mission objectives and identify potential gaps.

The study focuses on the blue dimension of the S3, considered as the entry point to identify priorities aligned with the Mission objectives. Nevertheless, we also explored other domains that could positively contribute to the achievement of Mission Ocean's objectives, in particular to tackle pollution of marine and freshwater ecosystems. Most of the regions studied include a blue dimension in their S3, whether directly through a specific area of specialisation²⁹, or indirectly, considering the sustainable blue economy or blue growth as a transversal priority due to the strong maritime economy of the region³⁰. In fact, although eight of the regions studied did not integrate the blue economy sector in their S3 as a specific domain or considered it as a transversal component of their strategy, relevant priorities related to the blue economy were included in their S3 2021-2027.

In the following sections, we will compare the objectives of Mission Ocean against the RIS3 strategies of the regions analysed to assess alignment and complementarities.

²⁹ Azores (PT), Norte (PT), Madeira (PT), Pays de la Loire (FR), Gozo (MT), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Puglia (IT), Murcia (ES), Brittany (FR), Sicily (IT), La Réunion (FR), Occitania (FR), Guadeloupe (FR), Lisboa (PT), Southwest Finland (FI), Pomorskie (PL).

³⁰ This is notably the case for: Galicia (ES), Crete (GR), Västra Götaland (SE) and Blekinge (SE).

2.3.1 Objective 1: Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity.

Among the regions studied, 12 included a component related to protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity (Table 5).

Table 5. Regions by Lighthouse area that include a component related to Mission Objectif 1 (Protection and restoration of freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity).

Lighthouse	S3 priorities including a “protection and restoration of freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity” (Mission Objectif 1) component
Atlantic/Arctic lighthouse	Madeira (PT), Lisboa (PT), Galicia (ES), Azores (PT), Brittany (FR)
Mediterranean lighthouse	Occitania (FR), Murcia (ES), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Puglia (IT)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse	Moldova
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	Blekinge (SE)
Outermost regions	La Réunion (FR)

Among these regions, four refer directly to the restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems: Lisboa and Vale do Tejo (PT), the Azores (PT), Occitania (FR), Murcia (ES).

In the four regions cited, the necessity to preserve certain strong natural assets influenced regional actors to consider their restoration as an important priority for the region's future development. We can take the example of the region of Lisboa and Vale do Tejo (PT), which hosts two important estuarine and coastal protected areas³¹, a natural and economic capital for the region. Therefore, regional actors intend to focus on the promotion and restoration of these ecosystems, such as with the installation of artificial reefs in maritime port infrastructure.

For some regions, we can suggest that certain priorities were raised in reaction to an important environmental challenge. In the case of Murcia (ES), for example, the degradation of the Mar Menor certainly encouraged regional stakeholders to include this priority in their RIS4 to restore this important habitat. This facilitated the emergence of organisations actively working on the issue of degraded marine ecosystems (consultancy activities) and pollution remediation³², and led regional stakeholders from the academic and private sector to specialise in this area.

The importance of reducing pollution and restoring contaminated ecosystems could thus be a lever to prioritise R&I investments in the protection of environmental assets. For example, in Moldova, the 2020-2023 National Programme for Research and Innovation transposes the principles of smart specialisation, with the elaboration of five strategic priorities in the field of research and innovation. Under this programme, the strategic priority III on environment and climate change foresees the development of programmes for restoring degraded ecosystems as part of its objective related to the

³¹ The Tagus Estuary Nature Reserve and Natural Reserve of the Sado Estuary - and the coastline - Luiz Saldanha Marine Park and Natural Park Sintra Cascais.

³² E.g., emerging pollutants, such as antibiotics and the effects of these pollutants on Posidonia meadows.

reduction and prevention of waste, plastics and pollutants.³³, which is therefore directly linked with the rationale of restoring ecosystems from significant environmental pollution.

In the other regions analysed, this objective is more geared towards developing marine protected areas (MPAs), preserving natural resources and ensuring connectivity between them, and developing a network of protected areas. We can notably mention the examples of the outermost regions, La Réunion (FR), Madeira (PT) and the Azores (PT), considered hotspots for marine biodiversity and which host fragile habitats that provide vital ecosystem services for the population.³⁴ On this aspect, the RIS4 of La Réunion (FR) and RIS3 of Madeira (PT) refer to the improvement of connectivity between habitats. Their insularity can reinforce the need to ensure harmonised conservation of those critical marine habitats and, in collaboration with neighbouring regions and countries, the monitoring and management of marine protected areas. The region of La Reunion (FR) receives support from the Interreg Indian Ocean programme to foster this cooperation. It has already implemented projects through this programme for the conservation of marine habitats and biodiversity.³⁵

The region of **Blekinge** (SE) integrated the EU Missions as one of their main areas of specialisation and will use EU Mission Ocean, EU Mission Climate Adaptation and EU Mission Climate Neutral Cities as a method to influence its S3 process and thus foster the integration of their regional innovative solutions within the EU and international value chains and reinforce their competitiveness. Through this integrated approach, smart specialisation priorities serve as a tool for creating innovative projects related to ocean restoration and Mission objectives altogether.

With the exception of the cases mentioned above, **compared with the other priorities aligned with the Mission objectives, restoration and preservation of marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity is scarcely mentioned in RIS3 for the 2021-2027 period.**

This gap can be explained by the need for more companies or technologies, developed in the regions, with a specialisation or substantial experience in ecosystem restoration, compared to the blue economy priorities, which are more focused on traditional maritime sectors. We can consider that this gap shows a need to generate more interest in ecosystems and biodiversity restoration, which could be fostered by a strong collaboration between regions on this aspect. Another reason for this could be the need to create innovative financing models around ecosystem restoration, which would make this sector rely less on traditional public funding models and not be looked at from a purely nature conservation perspective.

Also, the causes of marine and freshwater ecosystems deterioration are multiple (e.g., pollution, overfishing, development of grey infrastructure), which makes it difficult for regional stakeholders to prioritise innovation in restoration as a general objective. In fact, this would require identifying specific restoration needs for the different ecosystems and biodiversity of the region and collecting localised data on their environmental status.

³³ Annex No 1 to Government Decision No 281/2019, *Moldova 2020-2023 National Program for Research and Innovation*, https://mecc.gov.md/sites/default/files/pnci_engleza.pdf. Accessed 27 November 2023.

³⁴ Sieber I, Borges P, Burkhard B., *Hotspots of biodiversity and ecosystem services: the Outermost Regions and Overseas Countries and Territories of the European Union*, One Ecosystem 3: e24719, 2018.

³⁵ i.e. project on hawksbill turtles 'TimOI – Tortues imbriquées de l'Océan Indien' and project on the study of cetaceans 'Études des cétacés de la Réunion et actions de coopération régionale'.

Therefore, as Mission Ocean projects aim to develop and scale up innovation in restoration, following the advancements of the Mission projects will be relevant to developing this sector further and exploring innovative ways to attract investment, reflecting the important value of ecosystems in economic models. A certain emphasis could be placed on the Atlantic/Arctic and Danube/Black Sea Lighthouse areas, as both focus on the restoration of marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity.

On this aspect, Mission Ocean could thus be a tool to foster reflection on the adaptation of S3 priorities to the restoration needs. The Nature Restoration Law adopted by the EU Parliament on 12 July 2023, would notably offer a legal basis to further develop restoration activities and build on initiatives implemented among the regions to boost investments in this area.³⁶

2.3.2 Objective 2: Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters

The majority of the regions analysed include, in their smart specialisation strategy, priorities aligned with Mission Ocean’s objective 2 on the reduction and prevention of pollution (Table 6).

Table 6. Regions with S3 priorities linked to prevention and elimination of pollution (Mission objective 2) by lighthouse.

S3 priorities of the prevention and elimination of pollution				
	S3 Blue Economy Domain	S3 Environmental Domain	S3 Water Domain	S3 Agri-food Domain
Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse	Lisboa (PT)	Madeira (PT) Lisboa (PT) Galicia (ES) Brittany (FR)		Azores (PT) Norte (PT) Brittany (FR)
Mediterranean lighthouse	Emilia-Romagna (IT) Puglia (IT) Lazio (IT)	Gozo (MT) Murcia (ES) Puglia (IT) Emilia-Romagna (IT) Crete (GR) Valencia (ES) Western Greece (GR) Lazio (IT)	Occitania (FR) Murcia (ES) Crete (GR) Valencia (ES)	Occitania (FR) Murcia (ES) Valencia (ES) Crete (GR) Sicily (IT)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse		Moldova		
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	Pomorskie (PL) Kymenlaakso (FI)	Oulu (FI) North Netherlands (NL) Bremen (DE) Kymenlaakso (FI) Helsinki-Uusimaa (FI)	North Netherlands (NL)	Oulu (FI) Southwest Finland (FI)
Outermost regions	La Reunion (FR)	Guadeloupe (FR)		La Reunion (FR)

³⁶ Amendments adopted by the European Parliament on 12 July 2023(1) on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on nature restoration (COM(2022)0304 – C9-0208/2022 – 2022/0195(COD))(2), https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2023-0277_EN.html#title2. Accessed 12 November 2023.

We can also highlight that the focus of the Mediterranean lighthouse on the achievement of this objectives is mirrored by Mediterranean regions' strategies. Nine of them among the twelve Mediterranean regions studied include S3 priorities to orient R&I investments towards the reduction of pollution and the development of a circular economy.

As most of the pollution of marine and freshwater ecosystems has a telluric origin, land-based regional economic sectors have a crucial role in developing innovative solutions to limit the contamination of the environment and to shift towards a circular model to limit waste generation.

As this theme is transversal to different sectors, distinct S3 domains or areas of specialisation were identified, which presented relevant objectives on pollution prevention and reduction:

1. Environmental domains (*including plastic reduction*)
2. Blue economy domain
3. Agrifood domain
4. Water domain (*and water-related priorities*)

Specific examples of each domain above are presented in the sections below (see 2.3.2.1, 2.3.2.2, 2.3.2.3, 2.3.2.4 & 2.3.2.5).

The environmental domain is used here as a generic terminology to include the different thematic areas of specialisation specifically related to environmental issues.³⁷

As plastics and microplastics are the main focus of the innovation action projects of the Mediterranean lighthouse for the first phase of the Mission, the first sub-section will present the regions with priorities related to the fight against plastic and microplastic pollution, included in the different thematic areas mentioned above.

³⁷ The terminology varies among the regions studied. As a non-exhaustive list of S3 thematic areas on environmental issues, we could identify the following examples: Their S3 includes, for example, a thematic area on "sustainability" (Galicia (ES)), "sustainable use or resources for climate change mitigation and adaptation" (Gozo (MT)), "preservation of the environment and biodiversity" (Guadeloupe (FR)), "Green Economy" (Lazio (IT)), "circular economy, energy transition, climate action and biodiversity" (Madeira (FR)), "environment and sustainable development" (Sicily (IT))

2.3.2.1 Alignment towards sub-objective on plastics and microplastics reduction

Mission Ocean objective 2 includes two sub-objectives to reduce plastic litter at sea by at least 50% and microplastics released into the environment by at least 30%. Several regions explicitly refer to plastics and microplastics in their RIS3 (Table 7).

Table 7. Regions by Lighthouse area with plastics and microplastics S3 priorities

Lighthouse	Regions with plastics and microplastics S3 priorities
Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse	Lisboa (PT)
Mediterranean lighthouse	Puglia (IT), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Western Greece (GR), Murcia (ES)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse	Moldova
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	Kymenlaakso (FI), Bremen (DE), Helsinki-Uusimaa (FI)

This explicit mention of plastics and microplastics is directly included in their blue economy domain or area of specialisation, such as in the RIS3 of Puglia (IT) region, which specifically integrates an objective for the reduction of marine pollution from plastics and microplastics. The reference to this type of pollution is notably done in the S3 domain covering environmental-related priorities³⁸, with specific objectives related to the recycling of plastics (Murcia (ES)) or the use of bio-based materials (Emilia-Romagna (IT), Kymenlaakso (FI), Murcia (ES)).

The objective to reduce microplastics is also included in the water S3 domain, which is the case, for example of Murcia (ES), as part of wastewater management objectives.

We can also infer that for the regions which included waste reduction and circular economy priorities in their S3 as a general objective, the elimination and reduction of plastics and microplastics is indirectly tackled and will allow them to finance relevant, blue-related R&I projects in this respect.

³⁸ Murcia (ES), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Western Greece (GR), Bremen (DE), Kymenlaakso (FI) and Helsinki-Uusimaa (FI).

2.3.2.2 Blue Economy Domain

Among the regions that specifically identified blue economy as one of their S3 priority domains, seven included objectives for the reduction of the pollution of marine and coastal environment (Table 8).

Table 8. Regions by Lighthouse area with S3 blue economy topics

Lighthouse	Regions with S3 blue economy topics
Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse	Lisboa (PT)
Mediterranean lighthouse	Emilia-Romagna (IT) Puglia (IT) Lazio (IT)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse	N/A
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	Pomorskie (PL), Kymenlaakso (FI)
Outermost regions	La Reunion (FR)

2.3.2.2.1 Land-based pollution

All of them take into consideration the need to tackle land-based pollution. We can mention here the example of La Reunion (FR), which integrated a specific axis of R&I on land-sea continuum, to foster the study, characterisation, and quantification of sediments and pollutants from land-based sources which transit to coastal areas. The region of Emilia-Romagna (IT) specifically refers to the need to protect the marine environment from anthropic pollution in the S3 blue economy priority.

2.3.2.2.2 Sea-based pollution

Development of innovation to tackle sea-based pollution is envisaged by Lisboa region (PT), Lazio (IT) and Kymenlaakso (FI), on different aspects.

The region of Lisboa (PT) and Lazio (IT) focused on the recovery and recycling of marine litter from a large spectrum, including abandoned, lost, or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG), in the perspective of a circular economy. Lazio region intends to develop new technologies for the recovery and recycling of lost fishing gear. The region of Lisboa (PT) focuses on the reduction, reuse and recycling of marine litter within the circular economy framework, with the promotion of the use of new environmentally friendly materials in fishing gears.

Kymenlaakso (FI) mentioned the development of knowledge on oil disaster prevention and clean-up as one of their S3 priorities related to Mission objectives³⁹.

Regarding underwater/ocean noise pollution, some regions are keen to work on this specific challenge. For example, the region of Lisboa (PT) refers to this type of pollution in the strategic axis of smart maritime technology in the S3 blue economy domain. Another relevant example is the region of Murcia (ES), which is particularly engaged in the development of innovative solutions to tackle this form of marine pollution, although this is not included in its RIS4. Through the involvement of the Marine Technology Centre of Murcia in the project [QUIETSEAS⁴⁰](#), the region notably organised a summit in Cartagena in March 2023 on underwater noise management, gathering a wide range of

³⁹ Response provided to the questionnaire on 19 December 2022.

⁴⁰ QUIETSEAS Project: <https://quietseas.eu/>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

stakeholders with the specific objective of delivering a training session for non-EU countries on ocean pollution management.⁴¹ The specialisation of regional companies and organisations on this topic makes the region of Murcia (ES) a key actor at the European and Mediterranean levels, which could favour the engagement of other regions on this challenge.

2.3.2.3 Environmental Domain

Most of the S3 priorities in the regions listed below aligned with the objective to prevent and reduce pollution in the marine and freshwater environment form part of the S3 thematic areas related to environmental priorities. Among these regions (Table 9), the majority will develop innovation in the field of circular economy. We can highlight that several regions aim to develop innovation in the textile or clothes industry. The priority mainly refers to the development of more circular models in the production process and can, therefore, contribute to the reduction of pollution from this industry.

Table 9. Regions by Lighthouse area with environmentally related topics in their S3

Lighthouse	Regions with S3 environmental related topics
Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse	Madeira (PT), Lisboa (PT), Galicia (ES), Brittany (FR)
Mediterranean lighthouse	Gozo (MT), Murcia (ES), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Crete (GR), Western Greece (GR), Valencia (ES), Puglia (IT), Lazio (IT)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse	N/A
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	Oulu (FI), North Netherlands (PL), Bremen (DE), Kymenlaakso (FI), Helsinki-Uusimaa (FI)
Outermost regions	Guadeloupe (FR)

This is notably the case for the Spanish regions studied. The region of Galicia (ES) aims to develop sustainable textiles, which can include the reduction of microplastics from synthetic fibres. Murcia (ES) also intends to strengthen innovation to develop circular production models in the footwear and fashion industry. Valencia (ES) has already implemented relevant practices in the recycling field, notably developing a technology to favour the separation process of footwear materials to facilitate its recycling.

Although not explicitly stated in their RIS3, the region of Norte (PT) has a strong clothing sector and wishes to develop solutions to reduce microplastic pollution from the synthetic fibres released into the environment during the production process.⁴²

Several regions⁴³ already collaborate to further develop⁴³ and promote circular models in the textile industry through the I3 project [REGIOGREENTEX⁴⁴](#) (see section 3.3.1 on transregional cooperation

⁴¹ European Commission, *Summit on underwater noise management | 14 March 2023 | Cartagena, Spain*, <https://westmed-initiative.ec.europa.eu/events/summit-on-underwater-noise-management-14-march-2023-cartagena-spain/>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁴² Information collected during the interview conducted with a representative of Norte Region (PT) on 22 March 2023.

⁴³ Flanders (BE), East Netherlands (NL), Hauts-de-France (FR), Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (FR), Piedmont (IT), Tuscany (IT), Norte Portugal (PT), Northeast Romania (RO), Catalunya (ES), Valencia (ES) & Västra Götaland (SE).

⁴⁴ REGIOGREENTEX Project: <https://euratex.eu/projects-initiatives/regiogreentex/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

through I3). Therefore, we can consider that capitalisation efforts to showcase the advancements and results of this project might be particularly relevant to inspire other regions with a strong clothes and footwear industry to improve its circularity and reduce its impact on the environment.

2.3.2.4 Water domain

The regions that included a specific S3 area of specialisation on water, tend to prioritise actions related to wastewater treatment and the development of innovation to reduce water contamination and improve water quality (Table 10).

Table 10. Regions by Lighthouse area with S3 water priorities

Lighthouse	Regions with S3 water related priorities
Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse	N/A
Mediterranean lighthouse	Occitania (FR), Murcia (ES), Crete (GR), Valencia (ES)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse	Moldova
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	Oulu (FI), North Netherlands (PL)
Outermost regions	N/A

Several regions can notably count on strong organisations and companies that have already developed appropriate technologies for the treatment and recycling of water, such as the regions of Valencia (ES) or North Netherlands (NL). For example, North Netherlands (NL) region has a comparative advantage in water technology through water clusters or a specific water campus in the city of Leeuwarden.⁴⁵

Among the regions listed in the table, some have also included relevant S3 priorities that are water-related in areas of specialisation other than water.

Under the area of specialisation for a carbon-neutral and circular economy, the region of Valencia (ES), being one of the most advanced EU regions on the reuse of water, included a priority for better water use and management, with a specific focus on the treatment and reuse of water, which has the indirect objective to reduce water scarcity in Valencia (ES).

The Regional Council of Oulu (FI) included a priority on water under the area of specialisation on innovative bio and circular economy. Regional stakeholders identified this priority due to the fragile freshwater ecosystems of the region (important rivers and lakes), which have been particularly affected by polluting industries. Several universities and research organisations have therefore developed strong knowledge of water management, contributing to the specialisation of the region in this field.⁴⁶

The knowledge and investment of several regions in water management and the reduction of water contamination are an advantage to achieving objective 2 of the Mission Ocean. In particular, their involvement in the **S3 thematic partnership on water – Water Smart Territories**⁴⁷ – is a good arena

⁴⁵ Link to website: <https://www.watercampus.nl>. Accessed 12 November 2023.

⁴⁶ Information collected during the interview conducted with representatives of the Regional Council of Oulu on 29 March 2023.

⁴⁷ European Commission. *Water Smart Territories*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/water-smart-territories>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

for water technology transfer, notably to reduce and prevent water pollution and maximise inter-regional opportunities for collaboration in this field, with the support of some leader regions.⁴⁸

In addition, the current revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive⁴⁹ is planned to include new measures related to wastewater contamination, such as tackling micropollutants, monitoring the presence of microplastics or combating pollution from rain waters. The report from the ENVI Committee also advocates to promote the reuse of treated wastewater, and further tackle wastewater pollution, including micro-plastic releases from textiles.⁵⁰

Once adopted, the updated legislation could provide further impetus in the development of innovative solutions to improve water treatment and recycling, particularly in those regions that prioritise this issue in their RIS3.

⁴⁸ List of regions involved: Catalonia (ES), Crete (GR), Grand Est (FR), Kainuu (FI), Latvia (LV), Liberec (CZ), Lombardy (IT), Malta (MT), Norte (PT), North East Romania (RO), North West Romania (RO), Northern Ostrobothnia (FI), Oulu (FI), North Savo (FI), Occitania (FR), Olomouc (CZ), Rhineland (DE), Scotland (UK), Slovenia (SI), South Moravia (CZ), South Savo (FI).

⁴⁹ European Parliament, *Legislative Train Schedule. Revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive*, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-revision-of-the-urban-wastewater-treatment-directive-\(refit\)](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-revision-of-the-urban-wastewater-treatment-directive-(refit)). Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁵⁰ European Parliament, Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI Committee), *Report on the proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning urban wastewater treatment*, Report, https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2023-0276_EN.pdf. Accessed 27 November 2023.

2.3.2.5 Agrifood domain

The regions cited below (Table 11) have identified relevant priorities in the agri-food domain which can support the achievement of objective 2 of the Mission. The priorities under this domain or area of specialisation can be divided into two main priorities, one on the first stage of the value chain, with the reduction of intrants (pesticides, nutrients) and one on the last part of the value chain, with objectives to reduce packaging or develop innovative biomaterials to replace plastics.

Table 11. Regions by Lighthouse area with Agrifood domain/topics in their S3

Lighthouse	Regions with S3 agrifood domain
Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse	Azores (PT), Norte (PT), Brittany (FR)
Mediterranean lighthouse	Occitania (FR), Murcia (ES), Crete (GR), Valencia (ES), Sicily (IT)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse	Southeast Romania (RO)
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	Oulu (FI), Southwest Finland (FI)
Outermost regions	La Reunion (FR)

Indeed, it is worth mentioning that several regions (La Reunion (FR), Norte (PT), Occitania (FR), Oulu (FI) and Murcia (ES)) intend to invest in innovation that will contribute to the sub-objective of the reduction by at least 50% of nutrient losses and of the use and risk of chemical pesticides.

Although not explicitly mentioned in their RIS3, several regions might award innovative project proposals in the agri-food domain having this objective as an added value. This would be the case for, e.g., South-East Romania (RO), as stakeholders mentioned this during the entrepreneurial discovery process (EDP)⁵¹. Azores region's (PT) priority of fostering organic agriculture that promotes biodiversity certainly implies the reduction of pesticides and, therefore, less contamination of soils and water flows.

The priority to reduce waste and packaging in the agri-food domains should also be considered as a relevant action to achieve Mission Ocean's objective 2, by combating water and sea contamination at its source. On this aspect, we can mention the region of Valencia (ES), which strongly developed innovations to reduce waste from packaging and benefits from the work of technical and research institutes specialised in this field. The region of Sicily (IT) also intends to develop research, experimentation, and application of innovative technologies and/or solutions for the development of innovative packaging and smarter supply chains.

The **Smart Specialisation Platform for Agri-Food**⁵² could, therefore, be used as a good lever to foster inter-regional collaboration among maritime regions on the reduction of pollution in the entire food value chain and thus support the existing practices of regions to reach the objective 2 of the Mission Ocean and Waters.

⁵¹ European Commission, *Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP)*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/edp>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁵² European Commission, *The Smart Specialisation Platform for Agri-Food (S3P Agri-Food)*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/agri-food>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

2.3.3 Objective 3: Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular.

All the regions that integrated an area of specialisation or domain related to the blue economy sector include priorities aligned with Mission Ocean objective 3 of a sustainable, carbon-neutral, circular blue economy and contribute to the sub-objectives of 1) the elimination of greenhouse gas emissions from the maritime economy; 2) the development of a zero-carbon and low-impact aquaculture; and 3) the promotion of a circular, low carbon multi-purpose use of marine and water space. We also included in this category the priorities related to marine renewable energy development.

There is a clear interest in investments in research and innovation in the decarbonisation of maritime activities in all the lighthouses. Regional stakeholders have notably focused their priorities in the blue economy domain on the most traditional sectors, such as maritime transport, fisheries, and aquaculture, as these are one of their major economic assets.

In the three different categories observed among the S3 priorities related to Mission objective 3 (Table 12), we can identify the trends described in the sections below.

Table 12. Regions by Lighthouse area that include a component related to Mission Objectif 3 (Make the sustainable blue economy carbon neutral and circular).

Objective 3: Make the sustainable blue economy carbon neutral and circular			
	Marine Renewable Energy	Decarbonization of maritime activities	Aquaculture and Fisheries
Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse	Azores (PT), Norte (PT), Pays De La Loire (FR), Galicia (ES), Brittany (FR)	Madeira (PT), Pays De La Loire (FR), Lisboa (PT), Brittany (FR), Galicia (ES)	Azores (PT), Madeira (PT), Pays De La Loire (FR), Brittany (FR)
Mediterranean lighthouse	Gozo (MT), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Puglia (IT), Murcia (ES), Sicily (IT)	Gozo (MT), Occitania (FR), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Murcia (ES), Puglia (IT), Sicily (IT), Western Greece (GR)	Gozo (MT), Occitania (FR), Murcia (ES), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Puglia (IT), Sicily (IT), Western Greece (GR), Crete (GR), Lazio (IT)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse	N/A	Southeast Romania (RO)	Southeast Romania (RO)
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	North Netherlands (PL), Bremen (DE)	Västra Götaland (SE), Southwest Finland (FI), North Netherlands (PL), Bremen (DE)	Västra Götaland (SE)
Outermost regions	N/A	La Reunion (FR), Guadeloupe (FR)	N/A

2.3.3.1 Offshore renewable energy

Several regions (Table 12) are interested in investing in offshore renewable energy (ORE), which comprises wind, wave or tidal energy.⁵³ Among the regions that intend to develop innovation in offshore renewable energy, the main aim is to invest in offshore wind farms. Norte region and Emilia-Romagna have also included wave and tidal energy in this priority.

Mission Ocean stresses the importance of multi-use combined with offshore renewable energy, such as nature conservation and aquaculture with offshore wind farms, thus creating co-benefits from offshore renewable energy.⁵⁴ The Baltic and North Sea lighthouse notably implements innovation projects on multi-use scenarios ([ULTFARMS⁵⁵](#) and [OLAMUR⁵⁶](#)). The outcomes of these projects will be particularly relevant for regions with S3 priorities related to the multi-use model to share or identify relevant, innovative technologies to be scaled up. This is the case for the region of Brittany, which refers to the development of co-activities and the specific use of offshore renewable energy in combination with aquaculture, shellfish production, fisheries, biodiversity monitoring, tourism, and algae cultivation under the S3 priority on offshore renewable energy.

The existing S3 interregional partnership in marine renewable energy offers good opportunities for collaboration and fosters the uptake and upscaling of innovative technologies for the deployment of MRE among EU regions. Therefore, we suggest leveraging the current Mission Ocean projects on offshore wind (ULTFARMS and OLAMUR) and fostering a dialogue around other models of offshore renewable energy, such as wave and tidal energy.

2.3.3.2 Decarbonisation of maritime activities

Most regions with a blue economy area of specialisation identified priorities in decarbonising maritime activities (Table 12), which are an important area to develop interregional collaboration.

The S3 priorities identified in this field are mainly related to the green transition of vessels (fishing and other types of vessels), with the development of sustainable shipbuilding, the reduction of CO₂ emissions from the engines, or the electrification of vessels. Some regions also included the need to foster innovation in alternative fuels, notably in the hydrogen sector.⁵⁷

A relevant aspect to mention is the alignment of this priority with the specific objectives of the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) to increase energy efficiency and reduce CO₂ emissions through the replacement or modernisation of engines of fishing vessels. A regional S3 priority on this objective would be complementary with the funding of related projects under the EMFAF. As we will further explore in the second section, innovative solutions would be financed under ERDF PO1, and the EMFAF could offer complementary funding for the uptake and upscaling of innovative technologies.

⁵³ European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy, *An EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future*, Communication, COM(2020) 741, 19 November 2020.

⁵⁴ Steins, N, Veraart J., Klostermann J., Poelman M., *Combining offshore wind farms, nature conservation and seafood: Lessons from a Dutch community of practice*, Marine Policy 126, 2021.

⁵⁵ ULTRAFARMS Project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093888>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

⁵⁶ OLAMUR Project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094065>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

⁵⁷ The region of Bremen (DE) notably intends to develop green hydrogen with improved port infrastructures for the storage of this new alternative fuel.

2.3.3.3 Sustainable aquaculture and fisheries

Maritime regions are interested in focusing on selective fishing gear techniques to develop new technologies. In aquaculture, several regions aim to develop circular models and alternative fish food, such as the Azores (PT), Gozo (MT), Madeira (PT), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Pays de la Loire (FR), Brittany (FR), Lazio (IT) or Sicily (IT). The region of Brittany (FR) would also invest in the development of technologies for multi-trophic aquaculture.

The algae and micro-algae sector appear attractive for a few regions, such as La Reunion (FR), Madeira (PT), Västra Götaland (SE), Pays de la Loire (FR), Puglia (IT) and Brittany (FR). Due to the important environmental, economic, and social impact of the invasion of sargassum seaweed in Guadeloupe (FR), the region includes several priorities in the RIS3 to tackle this issue and valorise this resource (e.g. for the production of biomaterials, or as a fertiliser).

2.3.4 Cross-cutting enabler: Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System

The inclusion of a priority related to digital ocean and water knowledge (Table 13) reflects the need of several regions to collect further information/data, monitor, map and make predictions, to enhance their knowledge on natural assets and ensure their preservation.

Table 13. Regions by Lighthouse area that include a component related to the Mission Cross-cutting enablers

Cross-cutting enabler - Digital ocean and water knowledge system	
Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse	Azores (PT), Norte (PT), Pays De La Loire (FR), Galicia (ES), Brittany (FR)
Mediterranean lighthouse	Gozo (MT), Occitania (FR), Murcia (ES), Puglia (IT), Sicily (IT), Crete (GR), Lazio (IT)
Danube and Black Sea lighthouse	NN
Baltic and North Sea lighthouse	Pomorskie (PL)
Outermost regions	La Reunion (FR), Guadeloupe (FR)

On this aspect, we can note that some regions made efforts to develop research/observatory infrastructures, which offered them a strong basis to implement relevant projects related to the conservation or restoration of marine or freshwater ecosystems. For example, Madeira (FR) funded during the last programming period, under ERDF objective 1, a project to create the Madeira Ocean Observatory to develop fundamental and applied scientific research within the scope of marine sciences. This observatory offers the foundation to increase the visibility of research produced in the region and will notably be used to develop equipment to turn Madeira (FR) into a test bed zone for maritime technologies to diversify the activities in blue economy areas.⁵⁸

Through the project IDMAR, funded by the region of Sicily, under 2014-2020 ERDF PO1, which brought together the existing research infrastructures and the scientific-technological skills of the

⁵⁸ Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação, Tecnologia e Inovação, *Madeira Ocean Observatory (OOM) project*, <https://www.arditi.pt/en/projetos-finalizados/project-oom.html>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

organisations participating in the project, the region was able to create the largest distributed multidisciplinary laboratory for marine scientific and technological research in Europe.⁵⁹

The development of knowledge and data for the prediction of climate change impacts on marine ecosystems is considered a priority in several regions. Ocean literacy and interregional and international collaboration to exchange information (in particular for outermost regions) have also been identified as an important priority area.

Therefore, we can suggest that collaboration between regions based on this S3 shared priority could certainly boost the development of technologies to enhance ocean and water knowledge and facilitate data sharing among, especially considering the creation of the digital twin of the ocean.⁶⁰ On this aspect, Mission Ocean could certainly boost cooperation between regions, especially through the projects related to the creation of the digital twin of the ocean: [EDITO-Infra](#), [EDITO-Model Lab](#), [DTO-BioFlow](#) and [eDNAqua-plan^{\[60\]}](#).

⁵⁹ Agenzia per la Coesione Territoriale, *Idmar, con i fondi UE in Sicilia il laboratorio marino più grande d'Europa*, https://www.agenziacoesione.gov.it/news_dai_programmi/idmar. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁶⁰ European Commission, *European Digital Twin of the Ocean (European DTO)*, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters/european-digital-twin-ocean-european-dto_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

2.4 The financing of RIS3 for the 2021-2027 programming period: A benchmark of the funding instruments for regions

The mapping of smart specialisation priorities carried out through the questionnaire, interviews (Annexes 6.1 and 6.2), and desk research enabled us to identify the main relevant sectors for the achievement of the Mission objectives, where EU and non-EU regions would orient their investments for the current programming period 2021-2027.

The interviews conducted provided complementary information on the funding mechanisms used in each region to finance the implementation of their smart specialisation strategies. This section will explore the current practices from the region's specific needs in terms of R&I funding and opportunities.

It will also make some predictions in terms of relevant innovation projects to be awarded by the regions by presenting favouring aspects.

2.4.1 Relevant uses of the S3 by maritime regions favouring the creation of R&I projects aligned with the Mission objectives.

Smart Specialisation Strategies represent a relevant tool for the regions to evaluate project proposals in the field of research and innovation. Under the ERDF Regulation 2021/1058, the alignment of the R&I project proposals with the smart specialisation priorities is mandatory for the funds available under priority objective 1 (PO1): "A more competitive and smarter Europe by promoting innovative and smart economic transformation and regional ICT connectivity", in particular, the specific objectives 1.1 and 1.4:

- SO 1.1 - Developing and enhancing research and innovation capacities and the uptake of advanced technologies
- SO 1.4 - Developing skills for smart specialisation, industrial transition and entrepreneurship

In most of the regions interviewed, the calls for proposals under PO1 were not yet launched. Nevertheless, we can identify **two main elements** that would favour the creation of R&I projects aligned with Mission Ocean objectives, namely:

- The recognition of sustainable blue economy as one of the main S3 areas of specialisation
- Securing a multi-stakeholder regional community on R&I in the blue economy area

2.4.1.1 The recognition of sustainable blue economy as one of the main S3 areas of specialisation

In maritime regions, a sustainable blue economy area of specialisation would serve as a basis to facilitate the creation of R&I projects aligned with the objectives of the Mission Ocean and Waters.

Indeed, the priorities observed under the S3 blue economy domain of the regions cover all three objectives of the region: ocean preservation and restoration, ocean pollution, and a sustainable carbon neutral and circular blue economy. A dedicated S3 domain on the blue economy and sustainable blue economy would offer an integrated approach by covering all the different sectors and challenges of the blue economy. This would provide more flexibility in the elaboration of calls for proposals and thus widen the scope of R&I project proposals to a broader range of blue economy areas and anticipate future innovation opportunities.

For example, the S3 sectoral priorities of Southeast Romania (RO) on engineering and shipping and aquaculture and fishing would restrain the creation of R&I projects in these two main economic sectors. The region might thus update its strategy with a dedicated thematic area on the blue economy, opening the door to other sectors and innovation perspectives in the blue economy.

Among regions with a strong maritime economy, the blue economy can also be included in the RIS3 as a transversal aspect.

For example, in the region of Galicia (ES), around EUR 4.965 million will be mobilised for this current programming period to finance R&I projects aligned with the RIS3 (with EUR 2.965 million of public funds). Galicia (ES) has an important maritime economy, and most of its RIS3 priorities are related to the sustainable blue economy. The RIS3 of Galicia (ES) is structured into three main transversal areas of specialisation: sustainability, digitalisation and a focus on people. Each area includes, explicitly or implicitly, priorities related to the sustainable blue economy. The objective of the decarbonisation of the value chain can be applicable to the maritime/blue economy value chain, and the objective of the improvement, preservation, sustainable management, and enhancement of biodiversity would also refer to marine ecosystems and biodiversity.

In the case of Guadeloupe (FR), blue growth is integrated into the S3 as one of the three guiding transversal objectives and thus influences all the S3 priorities.

2.4.1.2 Securing a multi-stakeholder regional community on R&I in the blue economy area

The entrepreneurial discovery process (EDP)⁶¹ is a key lever to connect all the quadruple helix actors interested in collaborating on the blue economy and fostering the development of innovation in the most promising sectors. On this aspect, we can take the example of France, which, through a specific policy, boosted collaboration between R&I regional actors and the business ecosystem by offering the possibility to regional authorities to develop sectorial committees.⁶² For example, the region of La Réunion (FR) and Occitania (FR) took it as an opportunity to develop a sectorial committee (*comité de filière*) on the blue economy, gathering economic actors from the fisheries sector, tourism, R&I and biodiversity. In la Reunion (FR), this initiative started in 2019 and benefited from the project [OceanMetiss](#)⁶³. The sectorial committee on the blue economy notably integrates a working group on R&I, which joined the S3 network. The region intends to make a link between these committees and the governance structure of the S3 by mobilising the same actors working on very similar topics. The objective is to ensure a permanent dialogue between all these actors, within one structure focused on economic aspects and the other one more connected to research and innovation (S3). This approach notably favours the participation of companies/SMEs, who are generally reluctant to participate in a dialogue process on R&I. All in all, the sectorial committees can be considered as having a leverage effect in terms of stakeholder engagement in the S3 process and foster the elaboration of relevant project proposals likely to be selected under the ERDF PO1 evaluation.

⁶¹ European Commission, *Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP)*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/edp>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁶² République Française, *Loi n°2015-991 du 7 août 2015 portant nouvelle organisation territoriale de la République*, <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000030985460>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁶³ OceanMetiss Project: https://zenodo.org/record/3257422/files/20_SIMNORAT_Final_Conf_UFR_Potin.pdf?download=1. Accessed 27 November 2023.

The region of the Azores (PT) can also count on a dynamic network of stakeholders from the blue economy to elaborate relevant R&I project proposals in this area, for example, through research centres and private companies. The Regional Directorate for Science and Technology will not necessarily have to launch dedicated calls related to the S3 domain “sea and blue growth” to receive proposals in this area. This sector is very strong in the Azores (PT), and they can already predict proposals in this respect. Besides, the Azores government is planning to double the total area for marine protected areas in the next decade and the Regional Directorate for Science and Technology has already financed R&D projects on marine protected areas in the past. For this reason, potential proposals in this area can emerge.

Paving the way for an on-going dialogue and collaboration between regional authorities, SMEs, researchers and civil society representatives on blue topics can reinforce the awareness of regional actors on the opportunities offered by regional EU funds and will perhaps favour access of new actors in this cooperation structure.⁶⁴

The standard S3 regional governance structure includes working groups composed of quadruple helix stakeholders for each area of specialisation. A S3 blue economy domain would facilitate a regular dialogue of “blue actors” involved in a dedicated working group.

Therefore, the enabling condition for the implementation of SO 1.1 and 1.4 for a good governance of national or regional smart specialisation strategy and the criteria 4 on the functioning of stakeholder co-operation through the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process⁶⁵, represents an important opportunity for the regions to develop a strong ecosystem of R&I actors mobilized in the sustainable blue economy area. As the regions have the entire programming period to implement it, sharing regional experiences and good practices through PREP4BLUE could support maritime regions in this endeavour.

2.4.2 Synergies with the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)

The alignment of R&I project proposals with RIS3 priorities is mandatory under ERDF PO1 and notably SO 1.1 and 1.4. Nevertheless, smart specialisation strategies are used in several regions as an evaluation tool for project proposals under the R&I component of other European structural funds, such as the R&I component of the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) for example.

Some regions, like Galicia (ES), even went further by considering it as an eligibility criterion for R&I project proposals in all the funds available in the region, not only the ERDF. RIS3 is thus “multi funds” and “multi-managed” by the different services of the region.

Smart specialisation strategies are thus not only elaborated to comply with an ex-ante condition but to be used by regional authorities as a strategic tool for the planification of the innovation in the region.

This practice is particularly relevant to fostering synergies with the EMFAF. As mentioned in the first section, several regions included S3 priorities aligned with the objectives of this fund, such as the

⁶⁴ Barge-Gil, A., Nieto, M.J., Santamaría, L., *Hidden innovators: the role of non-R&D activities*. Technology Analysis & Strategic Management 23, no. 4, 2011. Pages 415-432.

⁶⁵ European Commission, *Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP)*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/edp>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

decarbonization of fishing vessels or the sustainability of fisheries and aquaculture, creating a good combination to finance those priorities through another funding instrument. Adding an alignment criterion of the R&I project proposals under the EMFAF with the RIS3 would create a harmonised system of innovative projects.

For example, the region of Pays de la Loire (FR) will support innovative projects for the energy transition of the fisheries and aquaculture sector through the R&I component of the EMFAF. The region will notably support improving energy efficiency and reducing CO₂ emissions from fishing vessels (through the modernisation of the engines, less energy consumption, and less pollution).

As a result, we can consider that a stronger involvement of maritime regions in the elaboration of the EMFAF expenditures on research and innovation would complement the funding for implementing S3 priorities for a sustainable blue economy. In regions where the S3 alignment is an award condition or criteria in the EMFAF project evaluation, strengthening the role of maritime regions in the preparation of this fund appears as a relevant way to maximise the impact of the RIS3 and harmonise the funding of innovation on sustainable blue economy in EU territories.

This aspect is particularly relevant as the EMFAF has been identified by the European Commission as one of the potential sources of funding for the first and second phases of implementing the Mission. Under shared management, the fund will notably support the achievement of the Mission objectives by developing more sustainable fishing practices, such as “innovative fishing gear” and “improved fisheries control and monitoring”, as well as collecting scientific data, studies, and monitoring activities.⁶⁶

2.4.3 Regional innovative funding schemes to boost innovation in the sustainable blue economy

Further to the practices described above, several regions finance research and innovation projects through specific regional funding mechanisms, complementing the EU structural funds to finance the implementation of their S3 and providing further support to SMEs and research centres to develop innovative initiatives.

This section therefore presents a sample of innovative funding schemes implemented in some of the regions studied. The list is non exhaustive, as relevant models have been also developed in other maritime regions.

For example, the region of Västra Götaland (SE) can finance innovation through its tax revenues. The region has around EUR 10 million that can be used to finance projects in all different fields, such as the sustainable blue economy. The region also provides financial support to many **science parks**, with one linked to seafood, thus creating a good environment for the development of new startups and small businesses. The start-ups can notably obtain “cheques” from the region to help them get a higher innovation level of their product and receive some guidance to upgrade their business. The science parks are mostly composed of actors specialized in business development, although some have a scientific background and may focus on the blue economy.

⁶⁶ Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030, *Implementation Plan*, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_for_publication.pdf. Accessed 27 November 2023.

Occitania (FR) notably developed “[Avenir Littoral](#)”⁶⁷, an innovative funding mechanism for R&I initiatives, as part of a framework agreement between the region, the national government and the bank of the territories (*banque des territoires*), to implement the coastal regional plan (*Plan Littoral 21*). Through the budget dedicated to the implementation of the plan, a certain amount is earmarked for the programme Avenir Littoral, which enables the region to finance innovative solutions for the sustainable blue economy. The fifth edition of Avenir Littoral will notably support innovation for the green and energy transition of the fisheries and aquaculture sector in the region, with a global envelope of 600,000 EUR.

Among the non-EU regions studied, we can note that Turkish regions are willing to develop smart specialisation strategies in order to orient R&I investments towards the main relevant sectors of the territory, such as the region of Çucurova (TR). Through the regional development agencies, initiatives to further attract private investments in sustainable blue economy have been developed. For example, the Eastern Black Sea Development Agency (DOKA) implements a crowdfunding scheme to facilitate matchmaking between the start-ups of the region and potential investors and offers them seed money to start their business.⁶⁸ As fisheries and aquaculture have significant potential in the region, this mechanism can support start-ups in this sector in developing innovative solutions and thus boost their development.

2.5 Main Recommendations and Findings

This section presents recommendations derived from the research presented in the paragraphs above. Those recommendations can guide regions in orienting and aligning their S3 priorities with Mission Ocean, collaborating with other regions and facilitating access to funding, and can also inform EU-level actors on the regional needs and how to align those to EU initiatives. Relevant EU-level funding and regional promotional programmes will be presented in the next chapter.

Recommendations to regions include:

- Exploit the full potential of RIS3 priorities on marine and freshwater ecosystems restoration: S3 priorities can be upgraded towards this objective, and interregional partnerships can boost the development of new technologies in this area.
- Most regions consulted have S3 priorities aligned with Mission Objective 2, on the reduction of pollution, which represents a high potential for interregional partnerships in this area. Regions are recommended to explore collaboration opportunities.
- Interregional partnerships on shared S3 related to Mission Objective 3 on a circular and carbon-neutral sustainable blue economy also have great potential:
 - Enhance collaboration on marine renewable energy and explore multi-use scenarios based on the BANOS lighthouse innovation projects.
 - Foster interregional collaboration on a circular and sustainable model of fisheries and aquaculture and the decarbonisation of maritime activities, with strong synergy with the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF).

⁶⁷ Avenir Littoral: <https://www.prefectures-regions.gouv.fr/occitanie/Actualites/Plan-littoral-21-lancement-de-l-appel-a-projets-Avenir-littoral-edition-2023>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

⁶⁸ DOKA - Eastern Black Sea Development Agency, *About Us*, https://www.doka.org.tr/kurumsal_hakimizda-EN.html. Accessed 11 November 2023.

- Another promising area for interregional collaboration is strengthening knowledge of ocean and water ecosystems, contributing to the digital twin of the ocean.
- Interregional governance can be improved with the creation of a R&I ecosystem of stakeholders specialised in the blue economy area.
- Further practices in the development of regional funding mechanisms on innovation in the sustainable blue economy should be encouraged (partnership state/region).
- A stronger involvement of regional authorities in the preparation of EMFAF expenditures would favour the harmonisation of R&I funding among the regions so that synergies with the R&I component of the EMFAF fund are increased.
- Furthermore, regional authorities can apply to be associated regions to Mission Ocean-funded HEU projects in different lighthouses, learning from pilot regions and receiving grants to conduct actions that tackle challenges linked to Mission Ocean's objectives. On this aspect, we can stress that the eligibility criteria under the calls for associated regions should be more flexible to provide the opportunity for regions from other sea basins to participate in the IA projects of the Mission, notably EU outermost regions. In addition, a dedicated website page to provide easier access to all the currently open calls for associated regions would certainly facilitate the submission of proposals from regional authorities.

3 Chapter 2: Overview of interregional programmes and initiatives for regional authorities and stakeholders

While Chapter 1 looked at regional policy priorities and their link with Mission Ocean, Chapter 2 will analyse relevant EU interregional funding and promotional programmes that can support regions in funding their local policies and forging collaborations with peers to spur innovation and increase impact. Some of these programmes provide funding opportunities, while others create networks and visibility for innovative (inter-)regional initiatives.

3.1 The Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE) platform and the Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnerships (TSSPs)

The Sustainable Blue Economy platform (launched in 2022) is the most recent of 4 platforms (together with Agri-food, Energy and Industrial Modernisation) created as “joint initiatives between several DGs of the European Commission that encourage regions and their innovations actors across the EU to build strategic partnerships, promoting complementarity of regional funding for innovation in specific smart specialisation areas”⁶⁹. They have their roots in the Vanguard Initiative⁷⁰.

Each platform contributes to building and hosting interregional S3 partnerships⁷¹, also called Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnerships (TSSPs)⁷². *“These collaborative networks have the ultimate goal of establishing European ecosystems for transnational and interregional collaboration in regions and countries with similar or complementary S3 priorities. Together, partner regions analyse and tackle various obstacles related to the implementation of their smart specialisation strategies. Thematic partnerships help regions improve their regional knowledge base, leading to new paths of development and a better position in global value chains and to transnational joint strategies of innovation.”*⁷³

Thanks to the recent launch of the Sustainable Blue Economy Platform⁷⁴, regions can collaborate in the framework of a TSSP to support their own S3 strategies.⁷⁵ Concretely, regions can decide to join

⁶⁹ European Commission. *Advanced manufacturing for energy applications*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/adma-energy>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁷⁰ VANGUARD INITIATIVE, *Who We Are*, <https://www.s3vanguardinitiative.eu/about/who-we-are>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁷¹ These partnerships are not to be confused with the Horizon Europe European Partnerships, which are of 3 types: institutionalised, co-funded, and co-programmed. In this framework, a Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership exists, whose acronym is the same as the Sustainable Blue Economy Platform, but they are two different things. To learn more about Horizon Europe European Partnerships, please consult: European Commission, *European Partnerships in Horizon Europe*, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/european-partnerships-horizon-europe_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁷² European Commission, *S3 Thematic Platforms and Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnerships*, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/communities-and-networks/s3-community-of-practice/thematic_platforms_en. Accessed 11 November 20,23.

⁷³ European Commission. *S3 Thematic Platforms*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/s3-thematic-platforms>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁷⁴ The first important event leading to the SBE Platform took place in Greece on 25 October 2022 following five thematic brokerage events on five topics: Blue Biotechnology, Marine Renewable Energies, Coastal Maritime Tourism, Aquaculture, and Fishery.

⁷⁵ European Commission, *Sustainable Blue Economy*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-blue-economy>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

or create TSSPs based on a continuously open call for expression of interest. There is no specific funding allocated, only technical support provided by the S3 Community of Practice⁷⁶. A TSSP could however be very interesting to foster collaboration and build proposals for accessing the Regional Innovation Valleys interregional funds (see dedicated paragraph below).

To launch a TSSP, regions can gather and prepare an expression of interest.⁷⁷ The call is continuously open and guidance is accessible for interested regions. Regions can also apply to join existing relevant partnerships in the perspective of the Mission, for example:

- **Water Smart Territories Partnership.**⁷⁸ This partnership focuses on infrastructure, digitalization, circular economy, and governance in the water sector, and its main goal is to strengthen the innovation capacity of European regions beyond resource efficiency. There is a clear link with objective 2 of Mission Ocean on pollution.
- **Smart Regional Investments in Textile Innovation.**⁷⁹ This TSSP's objective is to support a European sustainable and digitalized textile industry. It includes circularity, with a clear link to Objective 2 of Mission Ocean.
- **All the Agri-food platform TSSPs.** Indeed, fishery and aquaculture are two key sectors of the SBE and are part of any food-oriented partnership, with links with the three objectives of the Mission.

ADvanced MAnufacturing for Energy applications in harsh environments (ADMA Energy) and the Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) Partnerships. These partnerships are described in Chapter 3.

⁷⁶ European Commission, *S3 Community of Practice*, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/communities-and-networks/s3-community-of-practice/community_of_practice_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁷⁷ Submission Portal: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/communities-and-networks/s3-community-of-practice/call_partnerships_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁷⁸ European Commission, *Water Smart Territories*, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/water-smart-territories>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁷⁹ European Commission, *Smart Regional Investments in Textile Innovation*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/smart-regional-investments-in-textile-innovation>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

3.2 The Pilot Action for Partnerships for Regional Innovation (PRI) and the Challenge-Oriented Interregional Innovation Partnerships (CHOIRs)

Some regions have established collaboration through the Pilot Action for Partnerships for Regional Innovation (PRI)⁸⁰:

“PRI seeks to accelerate transformative outcomes by introducing local missions to coordinate actions under a single directional logic, exploring broad-ranging policy mixes for system-level innovation. PRI has a strong focus on innovation policy, but it also encompasses and inspires industrial, employment, education and social policies. PRI implies new ways of working across government departments and levels focused on addressing territorial challenges.”

PRI resonates with EU Mission Ocean’s transformative approach, and with the S3. Indeed, it is about “innovation-driven territorial transformation, linking EU priorities with national plans and place-based opportunities and challenges”⁸¹.

There are 74 territorial authorities that applied for PRI, a mix of Member States, regions, and cities⁸². The key idea was to integrate different funding instruments and actions in a coherent line of action, at local and interregional level. The interregional perspective was not so much present in the initial framework⁸³ but discussions and exchanges between the participants of the Pilot Action led to explore the idea of applying the PRI Playbook with an interregional perspective.⁸⁴

PRI participants also had a stake in the development of the concept of Challenge-Oriented Innovation Partnerships (CHOIR), from which originated the regionally focused Challenge-Oriented Interregional Innovation Partnerships (CHOIRs) idea in parallel. The initial concept of CHOIR was about proposing platforms that would be “additional to existing operational arrangements yet unite under the umbrella of common goals, currently disparate policy actions and funds, enabling complementarities between them and improving the likelihood of more needs-tailored, more timely solutions”⁸⁵. It was about proposing an operational framework in which different stakeholders (public at different levels, research, private, citizens, etc.) could agree on some goals and priorities and work together to achieve them. Illustration of a CHOIR framework below (Figure 3).

⁸⁰ Quote from: European Commission, *Partnerships for Regional Innovation*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pri>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁸¹ Quote from: European Union, *Partnerships for Regional Innovation – Lessons Learnt* [Flyer], 2023, https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/portlet_file_entry/20125/2023_03_20+PRI+FLYER+LESSONS+LEARNT.pdf/391f4b3e-ac56-dbb0-5a43-4024e2809e7f. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁸² European Commission, *Partnerships for Regional Innovation*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pri>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁸³ Pontikakis, D., Gonzalez Vazquez, I., Bianchi, G., Ranga, L., Marques Santos, A., Reimeris, R., Mifsud, S., Morgan, K., Madrid Gonzalez, C. and Stierna, K., *Partnerships for Regional Innovation Playbook*, EUR 31064 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-52325-3, doi:10.2760/775610, JRC129327.

⁸⁴ Quote from: European Union, *Partnerships for Regional Innovation – Lessons Learnt* [Flyer], 2023, https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/portlet_file_entry/20125/2023_03_20+PRI+FLYER+LESSONS+LEARNT.pdf/391f4b3e-ac56-dbb0-5a43-4024e2809e7f. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁸⁵ See page 44 of Pontikakis, D., Gonzalez Vazquez, I., Bianchi, G., Ranga, L., Marques Santos, A., Reimeris, R., Mifsud, S., Morgan, K., Madrid Gonzalez, C. and Stierna, K., *Partnerships for Regional Innovation Playbook*, EUR 31064 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-52325-3, doi:10.2760/775610, JRC129327.

Figure 3. Challenge-Oriented Innovation Partnerships (CHOIRs) framework

The idea of CHOIR was extended into CHOIR, adding an “I” for Interregional. A CHOIR is a partnership, which uses the CHOIR framework but applies it to the interregional level, meaning “an additional inter-territorial dimension to policy coordination, joint ownership with stakeholders and guiding directionality”⁸⁶.

From the regions that participated in this study, Azores (PT), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Galicia (ES), Norte (PT) and Murcia (ES) have participated in the PRI action, although it can be noted that there is a general predominance of Northern Europe in the PRI, initiative with all the Baltic states included (see map in

⁸⁶ European Union, *Partnerships for Regional Innovation – Lessons Learnt* [Flyer], 2023, https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/portlet_file_entry/20125/2023_03_20+PRI+FLYER+LESSONS+LEARNT.pdf/391f4b3e-ac56-dbb0-5a43-4024e2809e7f. Accessed 11 November 2023.

Figure 4. Regions participating in a Partnership for Regional Innovation (PRI) (Source: <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pri-map>). The participants underlined a link with the Regional Innovation Valleys (see section 3.3 below) and made the hypothesis that a PRI framework could be used to work concretely on these regional innovation valleys. The CHOIIR framework could also be very useful for new and ongoing TSSPs. Indeed, CHOIIRs could be the new model for upcoming TSSPs under the SBE platform. Regional stakeholders interested in developing a partnership should read the PRI playbook⁸⁷ and/or executive brief or connect with participants in the PRI Pilot Action (please see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Regions participating in a Partnership for Regional Innovation (PRI) (Source: <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pri-map>)

⁸⁷ Pontikakis, D., Gonzalez Vazquez, I., Bianchi, G., Ranga, L., Marques Santos, A., Reimeris, R., Mifsud, S., Morgan, K., Madrid Gonzalez, C. and Stierna, K., *Partnerships for Regional Innovation Playbook*, EUR 31064 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-52325-3, doi:10.2760/775610, JRC129327.

3.3 The Regional innovation valleys (RIV)

Under the New European Innovation Agenda⁸⁸, launched in 2022, the Regional Innovation Valleys (RIVs) aim to foster interregional cooperation based on complementarities, notably in terms of areas of specialisation (S3). Each regional innovation valley should meet the following conditions:

- *“i.) Enhance the coordination and directionality of the region’s R&I investment and policies, at regional level in support of key EU priorities and to address the most burning challenges facing the EU.*
- *ii.) Engage, building on shared or complementary smart specialisation areas (where applicable), in interregional collaboration to develop innovation, including deep tech innovation, and help increase innovation cohesion by addressing Europe’s persistent innovation divide between regions at different levels of development and/or innovation performance by including regions with lower innovation performance.*
- *iii.) Strengthen and connect their regional innovation ecosystems, including for example through joint innovation action plans to constitute connected regional innovation valleys building on their Smart Specialisation Strategies (containing milestones and targets) and, where applicable, on the participation in the Partnerships for Regional Innovation (PRIs)”.*⁸⁹

Regions can become RIV at an individual level but fundings are only available for consortiums and groups of regions. There are three ways of becoming a RIV:

- Responding to a call for expression of interest:⁹⁰ by being only granted the RIV status from the call for expression of interest, the region does not get funding or any direct service, but they are recognised as a RIV, which can have reputational advantages and support future applications for funding and collaboration. An online map⁹¹ shows all the regions that have submitted an application to the call.
- Building a successful Interregional Innovation Investments - I3 (European Regional Development Fund - ERDF) proposal (laureate)
- Building a successful European Innovation Ecosystems – EIE (Horizon Europe - HE) proposal (laureate)

Each region can decide to pursue one, two or all these ways to become a RIV. They are not mutually exclusive, but rather complementary. It is important to note that a region can become a RIV by its own initiative (using one of the three ways listed above) or can be proposed this status if one of its regional stakeholders (research organisation, company, etc) becomes a laureate of a I3 project.

⁸⁸ European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation, *A new European innovation agenda*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/066273>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

⁸⁹ Quote from: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Call for expressions of interest FAQ*, <https://www.horizon-europe.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/2023-06/call-for-expression-of-interest-to-become-regional-innovation-valley---faq-pdf-9119.pdf>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁹⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Call for expression of interest for Regional Innovation Valleys is now open*, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/call-expression-interest-regional-innovation-valleys-now-open-2023-03-28_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁹¹ European Commission. *Regional Innovation Valley - Matchmaking map now available*, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/whats-new/newsroom/24-09-2023-regional-innovation-valley-matchmaking-map-now-available_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

These valleys strongly resonate with the Partnerships and the PRI initiative. Indeed, partnerships are here to connect local innovative ecosystems and it is recommended to build a partnership (if not already done) before requesting a RIV label (call for interest) or RIV fundings (EIE and I3 calls). It is also possible to do it the other way around, as it fits the reality of each local collaborative situation.

Becoming a RIV can be beneficial for regions with stakeholders involved in the Horizon Europe demonstration projects funded by the Mission 2021/2022 Work Programme, as they could connect with other regions to scale up the solutions developed at a local/lighthouse level. The most funded regions by lighthouse in WP 2021/2022 and/or coordinators include: Bayern (DE), Berlin (DE), Bremen (DE), București-Ilfov (RO), Castilla Y Leon (ES), Lazio (IT), Centro (PT), Capital Region of Denmark (DK), Közép-Magyarország (HU), Nord-Ovest (IT)⁹², Norway, Ostösterreich and Wien (AT), Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur (FR), Schleswig-Holstein (DE), Western Slovenia (SI), South East Romania (RO), Flanders (BE), West Netherlands (NE), South-Western and South-Central Bulgaria (BU).⁹³

3.3.1 *The Investment Interregional Instrument - I3 Instrument*

The I3 instrument⁹⁴, part of the Cohesion policy, is specifically designed to promote the creation and development of interregional value chains, based on S3. **The expected project budgets are between 2 and 10 million euros** (Table 14). Calls are expected each year, making it easy for stakeholders to prepare in advance.

The focus is market-oriented: **70% of the total eligible costs need to go to investments in companies, with a focus on SMEs (TRL level 6-9)** (Table 14). The objective is to support commercialisation and scale-up of a specific topic/market and investments are supported by a market analysis or a business and investment plan. Projects funded under I3 encompass seed funding that the Project Consortium allocates to support companies that advance the status quo identified in the call and offer solutions to the specific challenge tackled by the project.

Table 14. I3 Key numbers and facts of the Interregional Investment Instrument (I3)

Key numbers and facts
<u>Programme:</u> Cohesion Policy
<u>Name of the instrument:</u> I3 – Interregional Investment Instrument
<u>Budget per project:</u> 2/10 M€
<u>Total funding:</u> 570 M€ (2021-2027)
<u>Type of project supported:</u> collaborative joint innovation activities in shared S3 areas, supporting value chains and investment.
<u>Example:</u> Baltic Muppets Project ⁹⁵
<u>Main advantage for the region:</u> Integration of quadruple helix stakeholders, interesting funding rates (70% or 100%)

⁹² This is a greater geographical region in Italy that encompasses the administrative regions of Piedmont, Liguria, Aosta Valley and Lombardy.

⁹³ Data from: European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation, *Dashboard Mission Ocean Portfolio*, https://dashboard.tech.ec.europa.eu/qs_digit_dashboard_mt/public/sense/app/630dc6b8-23f3-43a1-a275-7a59115f3813/overview. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁹⁴ More information can be found here: European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA), *Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument*, https://eisma.ec.europa.eu/programmes/interregional-innovation-investments-i3-instrument_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁹⁵ Baltic Muppets Project: <https://balticmuppets.eu/about/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

Opportunities in the framework of the Mission: the instrument makes it easier for different stakeholders, not only regions, to structure a value chain and then upscale solutions developed at local level.

13 funds are divided into three parts:

- Strand 1 – Investment and advisory support for interregional innovation projects in shared smart specialisation areas
- Strand 2a – Investment and advisory support for interregional innovation projects for the development of value chains in less developed regions
- Strand 2b – Capacity building for the development of value chains in less developed regions

Only strands 1 and 2a are related to Regional Innovation Valleys (RIV), with 570 million euros allocated for 2021-2027. S3 is at the core of the instrument focusing on three thematic priorities (in addition to deep tech as a transversal priority): green transition, digital transition, and smart manufacturing. Five areas are covered: reducing reliance on fossil fuels, food security, digital, healthcare, and circularity. The funding rate is 70% except for cascade funding/FSTP (Financial Support to Third Parties), if proposed by the project, with a funding rate of 100%.

Strand 2a will focus on less developed regions and on integrating stakeholders from these regions in existing or developing value chains, while Strand 1 will focus on already strong actors, regions and value chains in specific fields.

13 projects must centre around collaborative joint innovation activities in shared S3 areas, supporting value chains and investment by implementing three types of actions:

- Commercialisation activities bringing innovative ideas and products to the market (new to Europe, new to the sector).
- Testbeds and post-prototyping activities.
- Validation and testing in real environment (demonstration, innovation activities developed with end-users).

The eligibility conditions to apply for this call are:

- Strand 1 – at least 5 independent legal entities in 5 different regions of at least 3 eligible countries and at least 2 legal entities coming from less developed regions.
- Strand 2a – at least 3 independent legal entities established in 3 different regions in at least 2 eligible countries, and at least 1 more develop region in a project with strong involvement of less developed regions and focus on their needs.

The instrument can be used by any consortium of actors that fulfil the minimal conditions. However, it particularly fits the TSSPs.

3.3.2 The EIE Connect call - Implementing co-funded action plans for connected regional innovation valleys

The EIE Connect call (Table 15), published under the European Innovation Ecosystems (EIE) instrument, is part of the Horizon Europe programme. It is not clear if it will be published annually, however, the EIE instrument will be available at least until 2027 to fund connections between ecosystems.

Table 15. Key numbers and facts of the European Innovation Ecosystem (EIE) Connect call

Key numbers and facts

Programme: Horizon Europe

Name of the instrument: EIE – Connect (HORIZON EIE 2023 CONNECT 03 01)

Budget per project: 8/12 M€

Total funding: 60 M€ (2023)

Type of project supported: “classic” cascade funding with an interregional component.

Example: ACTT4COSMETICS Project⁹⁶

Main advantage for the region: Complementing local funding to promote regional dynamics (cofund call – 50% need to come from other sources of funding)

Opportunities in the framework of the Mission: this call allows regions to connect and fund their main local stakeholders based on a common interregional roadmap (joint calls)

EIE instrument CONNECT is extremely relevant to interregional collaboration and funding⁹⁷. The first call, which expired in October 2023, is a co-fund call with 50% of the funds to be provided by regional stakeholders. As it is for the I3 call, five areas are covered (deep tech is transversal): reducing reliance on fossil fuels, food security, digital, healthcare, and circularity. Project budgets are expected to be between 8 and 12 million euros (Table 15), lasting between 3 and 5 years.

The call is partly a cascade-funding call, providing financial support to third parties (FSTP). At least 50% of the funds will indeed be directed to concrete research and innovation interregional projects, implemented by stakeholders from participating Regional Authorities (joint calls will be designed and implemented to select the laureate projects). TRL 6-8 will be addressed by these FSTP projects, i.e., projects should focus on demonstration and technology, and business development. The limit is 600 000 euros per FSTP recipient and grant. This funding line allows regional authorities to co-invest in relevant close-to-market projects in specific areas.

The other part of the funding will finance coordination and support actions (CSA), including the design and elaboration of the joint calls described above. The eligibility conditions to apply for this first call are:

- At least five national or regional authorities from at least five different Member States or Associated Countries, of which:
 - At least two are representing a moderate or emerging innovator region and
 - At least one is representing an innovator region.
- 50% of the funds need to be provided by the beneficiaries.

The instrument can be used by any consortium of actors that fulfil the minimal conditions. However, it particularly fits the TSSPs.

⁹⁶ Not a project funded by this specific call, but project laureate of a similar Horizon Europe - CONNECT call. Project link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112710>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

⁹⁷ The European Innovation Ecosystems (EIE) instrument is implemented with biannual work programmes divided in three destinations, CONNECT, SCALEUP, and INNNOVSMES. Different calls can be useful to do interregional collaboration. Here we are focusing only on one specific call. Learn more about EIE here: European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation, *European Innovation Ecosystems*, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/european-innovation-ecosystems_en. Accessed 11 November 2023.

3.3.3 Complementarity with European Territorial Cooperation (INTERREG) programmes

The overview of interregional funding instruments, initiatives and programmes would not be complete without INTERREG. Indeed, amongst the regions studied, we could observe that INTERREG programmes offered a good complement to the implementation of S3 priorities aligned with the Mission objectives, and in particular the cross-cutting enabler on ocean and water knowledge.

INTERREG⁹⁸ is an instrument part of the European Regional Development Fund (we are on the 6th period of European budget programming including INTERREG so we talk about INTERREG VI). It is composed of different programmes:

- Cross-border programmes. The original and starting focus of INTERREG was about turning borders into opportunities and the cross-border programmes on INTERREG VI are the closed heirs of the first 1990 INTERREG programmes.
- Transnational programmes. These support larger-scale cooperation.
- Interregional programmes⁹⁹. These build networks to develop good practice and facilitate the exchange and transfer of experience by successful regions.
- Outermost Regions and their neighbours' programmes. These programmes are specific to outermost regions and include different EU neighbours.

There is not one single way to access INTERREG fundings, as the authorities managing the funds are generally regional authorities, each one acting slightly differently. Indeed, regional authorities are generally the ones drafting the programmes, evaluating the proposals, and selecting the projects together with other pertinent stakeholders.¹⁰⁰

Under INTERREG regional programmes, relevant projects for the conservation, observation and monitoring of marine and coastal ecosystems and biodiversity have been cited by the regions as relevant projects aligned with the Mission objective and funded through the 2014-2020 period.¹⁰¹ This has been notably the case for outermost regions, such as Guadeloupe (FR) or La Reunion (FR).

For example, La Reunion (FR) funded two relevant projects to improve knowledge on marine biodiversity, such as the TIMOI project¹⁰² to conduct studies on hawksbill turtles, or another research project on the study of cetaceans. The region of Guadeloupe (FR) notably led a EUR 3 million Interreg Caribbean project SARG'COOP¹⁰³ to tackle the issue of sargassum in the Caribbean basin. As the issue of sargassum is among the S3 priorities of Guadeloupe, we can identify here a good synergy made with the INTERREG programme, although not specifically dedicated to R&I.

For the 2021-2027 several INTERREG programme objectives are related to the Mission Ocean and waters objectives and would support the development of innovation in this area. For example, the

⁹⁸ Interreg, *Interreg 2021-2027: Fostering Cooperation for a Stronger Europe*, <https://interreg.eu/about-interreg/>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

⁹⁹ Interreg, *Strand of cooperation : Interregional*, <https://interreg.eu/strand-of-cooperation/interreg-c-interregional-cooperation/>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹⁰⁰ For example, in La Réunion : Région Réunion, *INTERREG: Présentation*, <https://regionreunion.com/sites/interreg/>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹⁰¹ Results from the questionnaire and interviews.

¹⁰² TIMOI Project: https://museesreunion.fr/wp-content/uploads/TIMOI_Short-news-1.pdf, Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹⁰³ SARG'COOP Project: <https://interreg-caraibes.eu/sargcoop>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

INTERREG Caribbean Programme specific objective 2 vii aims to strengthen environmental protection, with actions for a better management and restoration of biodiversity (including marine biodiversity) and the development of research and innovation projects in this area.¹⁰⁴ In the Baltic Sea Region, Priority 2 of the INTERREG programme 2021-2027 is related to water-smart societies and intends to improve the state of water in the region.¹⁰⁵ The 2021-2027 programme objectives of INTERREG Atlantic Area are notably related to blue innovation and competitiveness and blue and green environment.¹⁰⁶

INTERREG projects also favoured cross regional cooperation, specifically on smart specialisation strategies. On this aspect, we can highlight INTERREG projects that strengthened S3 governance and implementation, between regions from the same geographical area:

- The project [RIS3 NET¹⁰⁷](#), funded under the INTERREG MAC programme 2014-2020, supported the development of a cooperation strategy and a common governance system for the regional institutions in charge of the implementation of the S3 in the three Macaronesia regions (Azores (PT), Madeira (PT) and Canary Islands (ES)). One of the legacies of the project is the [RIS3 MAC¹⁰⁸](#) transregional platform for cooperation on S3 in Macaronesia islands.
- Under the project [IMPACT RISS3T¹⁰⁹](#), funded by the INTERREG Spain-Portugal programme, a transboundary RIS3 has been created, which strengthened cooperation and exchange of knowledge and innovation among many stakeholders on S3 priorities, with one area focusing on marine energy.
- A successful interregional collaboration on smart specialisation strategies was forged under the INTERREG Adrion programme with the [BLUEAIR project¹¹⁰](#), offering good opportunity of collaboration to Adriatic regions on the definition and implementation of blue growth S3 priorities, in synergy with the Adriatic-Ionian macro regional strategy (EUSAIR).

INTERREG therefore is a relevant instrument for cross-border trans regional cooperation based on Mission Ocean related objectives. Capitalising on positive experience from Interreg to foster interregional collaboration on smart specialisation strategies has been notably mentioned in the case of the energy sector.¹¹¹ Interregional collaboration under INTERREG can also be beneficial for less developed regions, which tend to be more active through this framework, rather than more competitive programmes such as Horizon Europe.¹¹²

¹⁰⁴ Interreg Caraïbes, *Interreg Caraïbes Operational Programme for 2021-2027*, <https://www.interreg-caraibes.com/program-interreg-caribbean2021-2027>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹⁰⁵ Interreg, *Interreg Baltic Sea region 2021-2027 Programme*, https://interreg.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/2022.04.29_IBSR_Programme-document_SUMMARY-1.pdf. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹⁰⁶ Interreg Atlantic Area, *INTERREG Atlantic Area Programme 2021-2027*, <https://www.atlanticarea.eu/page/77>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹⁰⁷ RIS3 NET Project: <https://ris3-net.itccanarias.org/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹⁰⁸ RIS3 MAC Project: <https://www.ris3mac.eu/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹⁰⁹ IMPACT RISS3T Project: <https://ris3t-galicianortept.eu>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹¹⁰ BLUEAIR Project: <https://blueair.adrioninterreg.eu/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹¹¹ Gomez Prieto, J., Perinaez-Forte, I., Palazuelos Martinez, M., *Capitalising on Smart Specialisation and Interreg, the case of energy. An overview between two instruments of the EU Cohesion Policy*. JRC technical reports, 2017.

¹¹² Woolford, J., Amanatidou, E., Gerussi, E. and Boden, J.M., *Interregional Cooperation and Smart Specialisation: a Lagging Regions Perspective*, EUR 30499 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020.

3.4 Navigating initiatives, funds and programmes

As described in the paragraphs above, many initiatives, programmes and funds for interregional collaboration exist. Regional authorities are the main beneficiaries, but they are useful for all the stakeholders involved in the Mission's implementation in the regions.

In the table below (Table 16), we have described the involvement of four actors (3 regional authorities and 1 other type of stakeholder to provide an example, here it is a university) in some of the interregional collaboration dynamics that we have described. The table clearly shows that different configurations and combinations of interregional funds are possible. Using the examples from the table below we can conclude that, amongst others:

- One region can be part of a TSSP but be not involved in the PRI or I3.
- Another region can be part of an I3 project when another can just be indirectly involved, and another not be part at all of I3 projects but be involved in a TSSP.
- A stakeholder cannot be granted the RIV label or be a participant of a TSSP but can benefit from the I3 directly, and from the EIE indirectly (cascade funding).

Table 16. Examples of different regions and stakeholders navigating the interregional funds and initiatives

Category	Name	PRI	SBE Platform	TSSP ADMA/MRE	TSSP Water Smart Territory	I3 Project "Sensing and Remote Monitoring in Marine Renewable Energy facilities"	I3 Project "Baltic MUPPETS"	EIE project (unknown laureates for the moment)	RIV label	INTERREG Central Baltic Programme
Region	Brittany Region	No	Interested	No	No	No	No	Maybe	Yes, by answering the call for expression of interest and via stakeholders involved in I3 projects	Not applicable (eligible to other INTERREG programmes)
Region	Basque Community	Yes	Interested	Partner and represented by a cluster	No	Partner and represented by a cluster	No	Maybe	Yes, by answering the call for expression of interest and via stakeholders involved in I3 projects	Not applicable (eligible to other INTERREG programmes)

Category	Name	PRI	SBE Platform	TSSP ADMA/MRE	TSSP Water Smart Territory	I3 Project "Sensing and Remote Monitoring in Marine Renewable Energy facilities"	I3 Project "Baltic MUPPETS"	EIE project (unknown laureates for the moment)	RIV label	INTERREG Central Baltic Programme
Other type of stakeholder	University of Tartu (EE)	Not applicable	Not part the main target group (regions)	Not applicable (but this stakeholder could possibly be involved in some processes and projects if its region would be part of the TSSP, which is not the case)	Not applicable (but this stakeholder could possibly be involved in some processes and projects if its region would be part of the TSSP, which is not the case)	No	Partner	Not applicable (but this stakeholder could possibly receive cascade funding if its region applies)	Not applicable (but the fact that this stakeholder is part of an I3 laureate project opens the possibility for the region to request this label that would be granted automatically on the basis of this I3 aspect)	This stakeholder is eligible and can access funding to develop projects with partners from other countries in the region
Region	Estonia - Eesti (EE)	Yes	Interested	No	No	No	Not involved directly as a partner but its S3 has been considered when the project was assessed	Maybe	Yes, by answering the call for expression of interest and via stakeholders involved in I3 projects	Participating in the programme governance, delegating the authority to a joint secretariat (based in Finland)

4 Chapter 3: Creating funded interregional collaborations: three examples inspired by the three Mission Objectives

In this chapter, we will present three case studies of interregional collaboration, funded by different funding sources. The examples below can help regions build collaborations and take advantage of the I3 instrument and EIE programme.

4.1 Marine Renewable Energy: a concrete example of a Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnerships (TSSPs) to make the blue economy carbon neutral (Mission Ocean Objective 3)

One of the objectives of the Mission is to reach a neutral and circular sustainable blue economy, specifically in the Baltic and the North Sea lighthouse, for which the production of renewable energy is crucial. This topic is addressed in the 2023-2024 Mission Work Programme in the call “HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-06 - Innovative nature-inclusive concepts to reconcile offshore renewables with ocean protection”¹¹³. The following example will allow us to illustrate how a TSSP works.

Offshore renewable energy is a sector described as crucial in a wide range of S3 across regions. It is also a sector that is already structured in a smart specialisation partnership, the ADMA Energy Pilot, making it an interesting case to discuss interregional funding with a Mission-oriented perspective.

The ADMA Energy Pilot is part of the Industrial Modernisation S3 thematic platform, one of the four platforms described in chapter 2. The ADMA partnership generated a project under the umbrella of the pilot action on interregional innovation projects (I3) about reinforcing the remote monitoring value chain for data producers, owners and users¹¹⁴. It is called “Sensing and Remote Monitoring in Marine Renewable Energy facilities”.

ADMA Energy means Advanced Manufacturing for energy applications in harsh environments. Regions gathered in 2014 through the Vanguard Initiative, and partnerships (ADMA Energy Platform¹¹⁵ and Marine Renewable Energy Platform¹¹⁶) were established quickly to make the EU the global leader in manufacturing of robust high-integrity components for marine renewables and offshore energy applications¹¹⁷. The methodology followed by the partnering regions is “learn, connect, demonstrate, commercialise”. The regions position themselves on TRL level superior to 5 to develop solutions ready for the markets.

The leading regions of the partnership¹¹⁸ are Emilia-Romagna (IT) and Lombardy (IT), both Italian regions. Other participating regions in 2023 are Asturias (ES), Basque Community (ES), Dalarna (SE),

¹¹³ This call is cross-basin.

¹¹⁴ More info here: European Commission, *Sensing & Remote Monitoring in Marine Renewable Energy facilities*, file:///Users/sto/Downloads/5.Josel.Hormaeche-Bilbao-TSSPEvents_2018.11.28_MRE-2.pdf. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹¹⁵ European Commission, *Advanced manufacturing for energy applications*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/adma-energy>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹¹⁶ European Commission, *Marine Renewable Energy*, Smart Specialisation Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/marine-renewable-energy>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹¹⁷ These two partnerships are covering mainly the same stakeholders, and have similar objectives. To facilitate the reader comprehension, we will consider them as one unique partnership in this report.

¹¹⁸ There are two partnerships, ADMA and MRE, but the members are mostly the same.

Flanders (BE), Friuli-Venezia Giulia (IT), Małopolska (PL), and Scotland (Non-EU, UK).¹¹⁹ They financed together the realisation of studies¹²⁰ to assess the sectors with big potential in the regions. Some stakeholders from several regions (but not all those involved in the partnership) have also worked together in European projects¹²¹ to develop pilots. They have decided to focus on three specific topics, following the results of the studies and taking into account the first years of existence of the partnership:

- Power transfer in the Sea, led by Scotland (UK) and supported by Basque Community (ES), Emilia-Romagna (IT) and Lombardy (IT).
- Joining of large-scale components, led by Flanders (BE) and supported by Asturias (ES), Basque Community (ES) and Scotland (UK).
- Next-generation materials, led by Asturias (ES) and supported by Basque Community (ES), Dalarna (SE), Flanders (BE), and Lombardy (IT).

The benefits of participating in a TSSP, based on the ADMA/MRE experience¹²², are the following:

- Identifying and matching complementarities/synergies.
- Deep analysis of internal capacities.
- Addressing gaps and weaknesses across the EU innovation investment landscape.
- Market-oriented approach.
- Paving the way for potential strategic alignment which will go beyond the development of specific projects.

Three key lessons can be learned from the experience of ADMA Energy for future partnerships in the SBE sector, linked with Mission objectives¹²³ :

- There is a need for political support (both at the EU and MS/Region level).
- A shared vision is necessary. Governance structure and working areas must be well described and accepted by all, a significant level of ambition should be pursued (political and financial commitment), and the situation needs to be assessed clearly and transparently (with mapping of competencies – analysing regional capabilities and gap analysis).
- No partnership is possible without a deep and continuous engagement from key stakeholders. Meetings and events must be organised to engage industry, RTOs, other research organisations, etc.

Other regions have links with the partnership, either because some stakeholders from their regions are interested and participated in a Brokerage Event on marine renewable energy organised in Santander on the 10/05/2022¹²⁴, or because they were part of the ADMA and/or MRE partnership at

¹¹⁹ Direct information given by Stefano Valentini, ART-ER, Emilia-Romagna (IT)

¹²⁰ VANGUARD INITIATIVE, *Advanced Manufacturing for Energy Related Applications in Harsh Environments*, <https://www.s3vanguardinitiative.eu/pilots/advanced-manufacturing-energy-related-applications-harsh-environments#demonstration0>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹²¹ Here an example: DOCC-OFF, *Scaling-up Digitalization Of Critical Components in OFFshore wind turbines*, <https://www.doccoffproject.eu/en/>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹²² Based on the slides presented by Aitor Mintegu during the DG Mare event “*Smart Specialisation for Sustainable Blue Economy*”, on 25th of October 2022.

¹²³ Idem

¹²⁴ Pôle Mer, *Smart specialisation for marine renewable energy : Atlantic Strategy National Events and EU Brokerage Event*, <https://polemermediterranee.com/evenements/smart-specialisation-for-marine-renewable-energy-atlantic-strategy-national-events-and-eu-brokerage-event/>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

one point: Andalusia (ES), Azores (PT), Brittany (FR), Canarias (ES), Cantabria (ES), Cornwall and Isles of Scilly (UK), Navarra (ES), Norte (PT), Ostrobothnia (FI), Skåne (SE), Sogn and Fjordane (NO), South Denmark (DK), Stockholm (SE) ¹²⁵.

The results from our interviews suggests that other regions could have an interest in joining, based on their S3 (some of them are also present in the list above, in italic): Azores (PT), Bremen (DE), Brittany (FR), Galicia (ES), Guadeloupe (FR), Gozo (MT), Murcia (ES), North Netherlands (NL), Pays de la Loire (FR), Puglia (IT), and Sicily (IT). Amongst them, it can be noticed that Azores and Brittany already have links with the platform, as it was stated above. They are indeed home to numerous key stakeholders' headquarters and offices, like Air Centre in Azores (PT), and IFREMER in Brittany (FR).

Other regions could also be considered, based on the map produced by DG MARE listing regions focussing on the circular blue economy (Figure 5)¹²⁶:

Figure 5. List of regions focusing on the circular blue economy (Source: DG MARE)

4.2 Biodiversity and Ecosystem Restoration – the need for a renovated TSSP following the recommendations of the Pilot Action for Partnerships for Regional Innovation (PRI)

In this paragraph, we will dig deeper into PRI and connect this initiative with Mission Ocean's objectives to foster collaboration. We will state as a hypothesis that the regions working in PRI and that have answered the survey – Azores (PT), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Galicia (ES), Murcia (ES), and Norte (PT)– have more chances and motivation to concretise interregional collaboration.

If we take a look at their S3 strategies, the Mission-related topic of preservation and restoration of marine ecosystems and biodiversity (Objective n°1) is common to four of them:

¹²⁵ It is a non-exhaustive list. Other regions could be interested.

¹²⁶ European Commission, DG Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, *Unit A3 Sea-basin strategies, maritime regional cooperation and maritime security. Smart Specialization for Sustainable Blue Economy - Stakeholders' thematic priorities for S3 partnerships - outcomes of brokerage sessions that took place in 2022*, Internal working document, 2022.

- Azores (PT) – under the S3 domains “Sea and blue growth” and “Tourism and heritage”, the region deals with different priorities with strong links with the objective n°1 of the Mission:
 - Promote the protection and sustainable use of marine natural resources (line of action).
 - Ecological restoration and preservation of geo biodiversity in marine habitats (transformative activity)
 - Promote the preservation and enhancement of ecosystem services. (line of action)
 - Promoting international cooperation for responsible and sustainable use of the Atlantic. (line of action)
- Emilia-Romagna (IT) – under the S3 domain “Blue growth”, the region deals with “Marine ecosystem and coastal area (environmental and safety monitoring, sea and port safety, protection and defence of coasts, marine habitats, areas, man-made and not, and ports).”
- Galicia (ES) – under the S3 domain “Sustainability”, the region targets “Improvement, preservation, sustainable management, and enhancement of biodiversity (including marine biodiversity).”
- Murcia (ES) – under the S3 domains “Environment” and “Marine and Maritime”, the topics of “preservation of biodiversity”, but also “sustainability of the marine environment” and “restoration of degraded marine ecosystems” are tackled.

Two of these regions are Mediterranean, two are in the Atlantic basin. The University of Vigo (Galicia, ES) is involved in the project “Coastal Climate Resilience and Marine Restoration Tools for the Arctic Atlantic Basin” (CLIMAREST)¹²⁷, funded under the 2021/2022 WP Mission call “Atlantic and Arctic Basin lighthouse – restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems and increased climate resilience”. For the Azores (PT), the AIR Centre is involved in the project “Blueprint for Atlantic-Arctic Agora on cross-sectoral cooperation for restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems and increased climate resilience through transformative approach” (A-AAgora)¹²⁸, under the same call.

Norte (PT) is also active in this topic and is listed in the Mission Baseline Study¹²⁹ as a region that could be active on Mission Ocean’s objective 1. For example, the project Ocean3R¹³⁰ was supported by the ERDF 2014-2020 programme with 588,185 euros. It began in 2021 and is implemented by CIMAR. The project aims to contribute to the Mission area “Healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters”, at a regional and global level, through the development of solutions to reduce anthropogenic pressures on marine and freshwater ecosystems, and to restore and regenerate degraded habitats along the North-West Portuguese coast.

It could then be a good opportunity for these five regions, together with other strong actors identified by them (partners in projects), to decide to launch a TSSP (in the form of a CHOIR as suggested by the PRI) on the topic of ecological restoration and biodiversity, under the Sustainable Blue Economy platform. Ideally, this could lead to an I3 and/or EIE proposal.

¹²⁷ CLIMAREST Project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093865>. Accessed on 27 November 2023.

¹²⁸ A-AAgora Project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093956>. Accessed on 27 November 2023.

¹²⁹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Baseline study for the implementation of lighthouses of the Mission ‘Restore our ocean and waters by 2030’: Atlantic, Arctic, Danube and Mediterranean lighthouses*, Independent Expert Report, Publications Office of the European Union, p. 349.

¹³⁰ Ocean3R Project: <https://ocean3r.ciimar.up.pt>. Accessed on 27 November 2023.

As it was discussed in chapter 1, the interviews, and the Baseline study¹³¹ also underline the possibility for other regions to join this partnership: Blekinge (SE), Brittany (FR), Centro (PT), Kymenlaakso (FI), Lisboa (PT), La Reunion (FR), Madeira (FR), Moldova, Pays de la Loire (FR), Occitania (FR), Puglia (IT). That would make a 15 regions functional partnership opportunity, ready to apply for some funding instruments (I3 or EIE Connect).

4.3 Developing an interregional collaborative framework to foster Mussel cultivation in the Baltic Sea

In the Baltic Sea region, we can observe a good cross-fertilization example from various Mussel related projects in the leading to a future-oriented joint investment project, which also points to new collaboration pathways and synergies between programmes/funds.

The examples are relevant for Mission Objectives 1) Decrease pollution and 3) Circular blue economy, and funding programmes covered include Interreg, Horizon, BONUS, LIFE IP, I3, plus national & regional funding in all countries involved. The actors involved are public, private and research.

In this case study, the INTERREG programme provided the initial funding necessary to ensure overall coordination, leading to the creation of the [SUBMARINER network](#)¹³², which ensured that key stakeholders from the Baltic Sea region had a platform to develop synergies, avoid duplication of efforts resulting in cost efficiency, transfer research to real-life investment and streamline results into an investment project.

The SUBMARINER compendium¹³³ highlighted, already in 2012, the potential of Baltic Sea mussel farming to mitigate eutrophication, and the advantages of using mussels as a regional protein source in feed/food or other commercial applications. While SUBMARINER already considered results from other projects such as 'EcoMussels'¹³⁴ and 'AquaFeed'¹³⁵ (both INTERREG) – a variety of projects were subsequently funded by various programmes – all related to Mussel Cultivation in the Baltic Sea Region, specifically:

- Baltic Blue Growth (Interreg BSR 2016-19) tried to kickstart commercial large-scale mussel farming in the Baltic by addressing technological, environmental, legal, and economic challenges. It operationalised 3 mussel farms with a total harvest of more than 100 tonnes in the Baltic Sea in 2018.¹³⁶
- OPTIMUS (BONUS 2017-20) aimed to provide robust evidence-based documentation (ecological, social, and economic) on ecosystem services and environmental impact of mussel farming to support its future expansion. The project showed that mussel farming is a highly competitive mitigation measure in the Baltic Sea.¹³⁷

¹³¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Baseline study for the implementation of lighthouses of the Mission 'Restore our ocean and waters by 2030': Atlantic, Arctic, Danube and Mediterranean lighthouses*, Independent Expert Report, Publications Office of the European Union, p. 349.

¹³² SUBMARINER Network: <https://2022.submariner-network.eu/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹³³ SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth EEIG, *SUBMARINER Compendium Web*, https://www.2020.submariner-network.eu/images/roadmap/submariner_compendium_web.pdf. Accessed 13 November 2023.

¹³⁴ EcoMussels Project: <https://projects.centralbaltic.eu/project/470-baltic-ecomussel>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹³⁵ Weblink unavailable

¹³⁶ SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth EEIG, *Baltic Blue Growth*, <https://www.2020.submariner-network.eu/balticbluegrowth>. Accessed 13 November 2023.

¹³⁷ BONUS OPTIMUS, *About BONUS OPTIMUS*, <https://www.bonus-optimus.eu/>. Accessed 11 November 2023.

- Rich Waters (LIFE IP 2017-24) demonstrated mussel farming as an in-situ measure for nutrient reduction of eutrophication of coastal waters in the Stockholm archipelago. The project supported BBG results that mussel cultivation is also possible in the Northern Baltic Region by using new adapted technology.¹³⁸
- AquaVitae (Horizon 2019-22) aimed to increase low-trophic aquaculture around the Atlantic Ocean; including a case study from the Great Belt, Denmark showing how blue mussels can be cultivated in offshore areas and how mitigation from mussel cultivation can also increase offshore fish farm production. The project developed new hatchery production techniques to find a solution for the low settlement rates of mussels, a key industry barrier.¹³⁹
- Combined Marine Aquaculture (Regional funding 2019-23) tested the combination of a blue mussel production process with fish farming in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern (DE).¹⁴⁰
- SNOOP (2018-2020, Formas) compared current & future bioeconomy activities that may contribute to the recovery and reuse of N/P including mussel farming as a case study in Sweden.¹⁴¹

During the final Baltic Blue Growth conference, partners transferred the responsibility for the continuous exploitation of the project's results to SUBMARINER, which acts as a cooperation platform within the Baltic Sea. With the help of the 'Blue Platform' project (INTERREG BSR, 2018-2022) SUBMARINER also acquired the necessary financial resources to coordinate the so-called 'Mussel Working Group'; a voluntary group bringing together researchers, farmers, users, NGOs and policymakers and encouraging its members to compare results and explore synergies between these different projects.

This work resulted in a joint position paper based on datasets of the various projects mentioned above, which provided a much more consolidated picture.¹⁴²

The ongoing exchange among the various stakeholders did not only create trust, but also produced a clear pathway for the future next steps to be taken. This meant that once the funding opportunity of the first interregional innovation investment fund call was published, the stakeholders involved were able to prepare a successful application within less than one month, resulting in the 7.2 Mio € I3 Baltic Muppets project.

Already within its first year of implementation, project partners have applied for other complementary funds at the national and EU-wide level (i.e., Swedish research funding) to allow further investments.

This case study highlights the importance of several elements for successful interregional multistakeholder collaboration:

¹³⁸ Rich Waters, *LIFE IP Rich Waters*, <https://www.richwaters.se/category/en/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹³⁹ AquaVitae Project: <https://aquavitaeproject.eu>. Accessed 27 November 2023.

¹⁴⁰ Landesforschungsanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Fischerei Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, *Kombinierte marine Aquakultur - Erprobung eines Miesmuschelproduktionsverfahrens in Kombination mit einer Fischzucht für eine dezentrale Aquakultur in MV*, www.landwirtschaft-mv.de/Fachinformationen/?id=1023&processor=processor.sa.lfaforenbeitrag. Accessed 11 November 2023.

¹⁴¹ Sustainable development, environmental science and engineering (SEED), *Marine bioeconomy for circular nitrogen and phosphorus flows in Sweden: Alternatives, hurdles and policy tools*, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2021, <https://www.kth.se/en/seed/forskning/ali/pagaende-forskningsprojekt/marine-bioeconomy-1.922864>. Accessed 12 November 2023.

¹⁴² *Position paper on aquaculture legislation in the Baltic Sea region*. <https://interreg-baltic.eu/project/blue-platform>. Accessed 15 October 2023.

- One clear joint theme – but supported by more than eight different funding sources (national, philanthropic, sea-basin, European)
- Successful interaction between researchers and startups / entrepreneurs
- One coordinating body, supported by projects designed to encourage exploitation and cross-fertilisation between results.
- High level of trust created through long-term interactions / commitments.
- Solid scientific evidence created through data sharing among different projects.
- Solid pathway for future exploitation and community building, resulting in a successful project.

5 Conclusions

Through its in-depth analysis of the Smart Specialisation Strategy priorities of several regions in Europe and beyond, this report has shed light on the most promising areas for further action in support of Mission Ocean, elucidating how regions can use planning tools, like S3, to contribute to and align with Mission Ocean’s objectives, and to seize opportunities when it comes to the advancement and funding of maritime restoration, pollution reduction and sustainable blue economy policies. The analysis of funding sources and knowledge exchange platforms clearly defines pathways for regions to collaborate and gain visibility to innovate in the blue field and support Mission Ocean. It is important that regions are aware of all the opportunities presented by different local and EU-level instruments and know how to use and connect them. If they do, they can take advantage of different funding mechanisms, including interregional funding instruments that can facilitate collaboration with other regions. As described in the report, some support instruments do not offer direct funding but rather the possibility for regions to work together and obtain visibility and credibility in light of accessing funding and preparing joint applications. For example, initiatives, such as the Sustainable Blue Economy Platform, give opportunities for regions to connect more easily than before. Mission Ocean is not running in parallel but together with them. The figure below (Figure 6) describes a theoretical flow of how regions can connect different instruments, policies and initiatives, using them as building blocks to support their sustainable blue development.

Figure 6. Regional collaboration and partnership-building theoretical flow

The European Commission and the Joint Research Centre have been building, together with Member States, regional Authorities and stakeholders a vast and quite complex framework for interregional financing and collaboration. And this framework is still changing rapidly: the Partnerships for Regional Innovation (PRI) Pilot Action is a good illustration with the emergence of Challenge-Oriented Interregional Innovation Partnerships (CHOIR). This framework is characterised by a certain flexibility: there are not many conditions and requirements to creating a Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnership (TSSP) or becoming a Regional Innovation Valley (RIV). Regional authorities must be proactive to take advantage of the different programmes, funds, and dynamics. This report shows that regions with one or more S3 Mission-related priorities in common can launch together a TSSP under the Sustainable Blue Economy Platform, which will facilitate starting or furthering discussions between

stakeholders. The starting phase requires a financial investment from the regions (time spent by regional stakeholders, meetings organisation including travelling, money spent for implementing studies, etc) but it can lead to the drafting of an I3 or EIE project, concrete direct (funds, demonstrators, etc.) and indirect benefits (value chains and business development, drafting of other projects using other sources of fundings, etc.).

This report proposes the launch of an Ecosystem Restoration and Biodiversity TSSP, to complement the current actions carried out under Objective 1 of the Mission. Based on their priorities, Azores (PT), Emilia-Romagna (IT), Galicia (ES), Murcia (ES), and Norte (PT) could be good candidates to lead this endeavour.

Three final conclusions can be drawn from the findings of this report:

1. There is a need for clear political support at national and regional level to sustain reaching the ambitious objectives of Mission Ocean. Mission Ocean could provide the necessary EU-level framework to mobilise such support.
2. A shared vision is necessary. Governance structure and working areas must be well described and accepted by all, a significant level of ambition should be pursued (political and financial commitment), and the situation must be assessed clearly through mapping competencies and gap analysis. CHOIIR could be a good framework on which to build.
3. No partnership is possible without a meaningful and continuous engagement from key stakeholders. Regions need to use the support available at EU and national level to act as innovation hubs, engaging the industry, RTOs, other research organisations and citizens to catalyse efforts towards the objectives of Mission Ocean.

6 ANNEXES

6.1 Annex 1: Questionnaire – Regional Smart Specialisation Strategies and the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters: A mapping of regional priorities for 2021-2027

In the framework of the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme for 2021-2027, the European Commission launched the [Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters'](#) (Mission Ocean), which has the overarching goal to restore the health of our ocean and waters by 2030. To achieve this, the Mission is articulated around the following three main objectives:

1. Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity;
2. Prevent and eliminate pollution (i.e., marine litter);
3. Achieve a carbon neutral and circular blue economy (i.e., by increasing low-trophic aquaculture and multi-use).

Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) are seen as a valuable tool to orient regional investments towards the Mission goals. Conducted as part of the project [PREP4BLUE](#), which supports the Mission's development, this questionnaire aims to identify how the Smart Specialisation Strategies of regional and national authorities relate to the objectives of the Mission Ocean. The questionnaire also includes questions related to funding opportunities, business engagement and regulation and policy.

Your contribution to the questionnaire will provide key insights on how to foster an enabling environment for the implementation of the Mission Ocean, especially from a regulatory and economic perspective. Results will also be used to provide recommendations on how to make the best use of different funding mechanisms to support the Mission Ocean and especially future demonstration projects.

We kindly invite you to share the survey within your network in the region, should certain questions require a specific expertise.

Please provide all relevant links in English and if not available, in your own language. Responses should be also submitted in English. Replying to this questionnaire should take you between 20 to 30 minutes.

The CPMR maritime team thank you in advance for your valuable contribution. Please send your contribution to: **Justine Brossard**, CPMR Project and Policy Officer Justine.brossard@crpm.org and **Giuseppe Sciacca**, CPMR Director for Maritime Affairs and Climate Giuseppe.sciacca@crpm.org

Some context about your region

1. Does your region have a Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) covering the new programming period 2021-2027?

- YES
 NO

If so, could you please share the official strategy document with us? (Ideally as a download link, together with a summary in English, if available)

2. Is your region involved in the JRC [Smart Specialisation Platform](#) and notably does it participate in one of the interregional partnerships?

- YES, please specify

- NO

The influence of the Mission Ocean and Waters in the S3 elaboration process for 2021-2027

3. Were you aware of the Mission Ocean and Waters when elaborating your new S3 for 2021-2027?

- Yes
 No (continue with question 4)

4. If not, what was the reason why you were not familiar with the Mission framework and objectives?

- Lack of information
 Lack of time
 Difficulties to identify potential links with the S3
 Other, please specify

5. Did the Mission Ocean have a particular influence on the elaboration of your S3 for 2021-2027, especially during the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP)?

The EDP is an inclusive and evidence-based process through which stakeholders will produce relevant information on potential new activities and thus contribute to the elaboration of targeted research and innovation policy. Further information on EDP can be found [here](#).

- Yes
 No

If yes, could you please provide an example that reflects this influence? Please specify or skip to the next question.

Identification of S3 priorities aligned with the Mission objectives and sub-targets

6. Did your region choose sustainable blue economy as a dedicated priority in the S3 2021-2027?

- YES
 NO

7. If not, do you think that there is nevertheless a link between your chosen S3 priorities and the achievement of some of the Mission Ocean and Waters objectives, sub-targets or cross-cutting enablers?

- YES
 NO

8. If you selected yes to one or both of the two questions, are the regional investment priorities directly related to any of the below topics linked to the Mission objectives and sub-targets? Please select all relevant topics.

- 1. Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity
- 2. Protect a minimum of 30% of the EU's sea area and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network
- 3. Strictly protect at least 10% of the EU's sea area
- 4. Restore at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers
- 5. Contribute to relevant upcoming marine nature restoration targets including degraded seabed habitats and coastal ecosystems
- 6. Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters
- 7. Reduce by at least 50% plastic litter at sea
- 8. Reduce by at least 30% microplastics released into the environment
- 9. Reduce by at least 50% nutrient losses, the use and risk of chemical pesticides
- 10. Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular
- 11. Eliminate greenhouse gas emissions from maritime economic activities in the EU and sequester those emissions that cannot be avoided
- 12. Develop zero-carbon and low-impact aquaculture
- 13. Promote circular, low carbon multi-purpose use of marine and water space
- 14. Ocean knowledge, monitoring or forecasting

If you have selected one of these options, could you please provide at least one example, with the number of the corresponding option?

Development of business models and methods of interaction with the business community

The Mission objectives will be only reachable if the private sector is involved. If you replied 'yes' to question 6, the following questions aim to identify viable business models for S3 priorities in the sustainable blue economy sector. Therefore, we would like to ask you to share your experience and ideas on how to engage the business community in the pursuit of your blue-related S3 priorities.

- 9. Does your region have collaboration models in place with the business community to support your Smart Specialisation Strategy and the Mission Ocean objectives? Please select one or more of the following options:**

- Partnerships, which foster the integration of ecosystem restoration in the economic value of blue economy operations
- Carbon capture and storage
- Incentives and regulations for public-private partnerships
- Involvement of the business community (e.g., fishermen, algae producers, etc.) through participatory approaches
- Partnerships for data collection, visualisation and use
- Other, please specify

- 10. Could you please provide one or more examples of the above that you either experienced first-hand or came across through your work and contacts? Please feel free to provide weblinks (also in local languages). Please specify or skip to the next question**

Regulation and policy

The PREP4BLUE project foresees a mapping of existing policies and regulations with an emphasis on those that have a direct impact on the implementation of the Mission by reinforcing regulatory enablers and/or addressing regulatory obstacles.

- 11. Beyond S3, did your region develop any other policies that support the Mission objectives?**

- YES
- NO

If yes, please provide one example or skip to the next question.

- 12. With regard to the activities foreseen in your region aligned with the Mission objectives, is there any particular policy or regulation that hinders or supports this? If so, please select the scale and, if possible, provide one example.**

- a. Policy or regulation that supports your activities**

- Local
- Regional
- National
- European
- International

- b. Policy or regulation that hinders your activities**

- Local
- Regional
- National

- European
- International

Funding opportunities

PREP4BLUE will elaborate recommendations on public/private funding models and instruments that support the achievement of the Mission Ocean's objectives. Existing funding programmes will be mapped and analysed to identify gaps between funding needs and funding opportunities.

- 13. Could you please provide one example of a successful funding model (projects, public/private partnerships, innovative funding model...) that you are aware of, and which could be analysed in this context? If available, please provide a link to the information website.**

Your Region in the Mission Charter

A major component of the Mission Ocean is to foster stakeholder engagement, for which the European Commission launched in June 2022, [the Mission Implementation Charter](#). The Charter enables stakeholders to express their commitments towards the achievement of the Mission objectives. It enables the European Commission to better engage with and support these stakeholder actions. The following questions will allow us to gain a better understanding on whether this message has already reached your region and to identify groups of stakeholders.

- 14. To what extent is your region aware of the Mission Ocean and Waters Charter? Please select one of the following options:**

- Not aware at all
- Slightly
- To some extent
- To a great extent

- 15. In case you are at least slightly aware, is your region aware of the purpose of submitting actions under the Mission Ocean and Waters Charter? Please select one of the following options:**

- Not aware at all
- Slightly
- To some extent
- To a great extent

- 16. Does your region plan to submit an action to the Mission Charter platform? If so, could you please provide a brief presentation of the action.**

- 17. Mobilising regional stakeholders would foster the bottom-up approach of the Mission to develop tailor made R&I solutions in each lighthouse. In order to target potential opportunities in terms of stakeholder engagement, can you identify in your region key organisations and/or entities to contact in relation to the Mission Ocean and Waters. Please only provide the name of the organisation and a link to their website if possible.**

Follow-up interviews

In order to get concrete feedback from the regions on the relation between their S3 and the Mission Ocean and Waters, we would like to contact you for informal bilateral interviews that will be conducted in the first quarter of 2023. If need be, you could suggest another interlocutor for a follow-up interview. A possible workshop on Smart Specialisation Strategies is also foreseen to encourage fruitful debates and foster collaboration.

18. Would you like to be involved in the following steps of this exercise, either for a follow-up interview or a potential participation in a workshop?

- YES
 NO

Identification of potential support

The following question aims to identify specific needs in your region as part of the Mission, in order to tailor the support to be offered to regional stakeholders via the activities of Prep4Blue and/or other Mission support actions in the different sea basins.

19. If you have faced some difficulties answering this survey, would you need specific support in relation to the Mission Ocean and Waters? If yes, could you please indicate the specific support needed.

- YES
 NO

General Information

- Mr
 Ms

Full Name:

Name of the Region, organisation, State

Position within the Region/Organisation:

Email:

Specific comments

Thank you very much for your time. If you have specific comments, please let us know in the section below. We will be in touch very soon!

6.2 INTERVIEW QUESTIONS - Regional Smart Specialisation Strategies and the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters: A mapping of regional priorities for 2021-2027

**INTERVIEW QUESTIONS - Regional Smart Specialisation Strategies and the EU Mission
Restore our Ocean and Waters: A mapping of regional priorities for 2021-2027**

Region:

Country:

Mission lighthouse:

Information on the region and the interviewee

REGION	
COUNTRY	
MARITIME BASIN	
PERSON INTERVIEWED	
SERVICE	
TITLE	
CONTACT DETAILS	

Governance

Competences of the region on S3	National	
	Regional	
Competences of the region in the management of funds related to R&I	EU Funds (ESIF)	
	National	
Preparation phase and Entrepreneurial Discovery Process	Which stakeholders are consulted?	
	Which entity oversees the drafting of the S3?	
Implementation phase	Which entity oversees the implementation of the S3?	
	Which service decides the allocation of funding towards the S3 priorities?	

S3 2021-2027

Global S3 envelope for 2021-2027		AMOUNT	FUNDING CATEGORY	BENEFICIARIES
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S3 priorities non-related to the sustainable blue economy

Context of the priorities and potential projects on R&I	Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity	
	Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters	
	Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular	
	Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System	
Support from the region apart from R&I projects	<i>Contracts with sectors</i>	
	<i>Direct support to businesses / research entities</i>	
	<i>Other</i>	

S3 priorities related to the sustainable blue economy

Context of the priorities and potential projects on R&I	Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity	
	Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters	
	Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular	
	Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System	
Support from the region apart from R&I projects	<i>Contracts with sectors</i>	
	<i>Support to businesses / research entities</i>	
	<i>Other</i>	

S3 2014-2020

Global S3 envelope for 2014-2020		AMOUNT	FUNDING category	BENEFICIARIES
R&I Projects aligned with the Mission Ocean and Waters objectives	Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity			
	Prevent and eliminate pollution of our			

	ocean, seas and waters				
	Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular				
	Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System				

Other questions

S3 Platform and involvement in interregional cooperation models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Involvement in the S3 platform Involvement in the PRI pilot action Involvement in S3 thematic interregional partnerships Other significant inter-regional collaborations 	
Mission Implementation Charter	YES	
	NO	
Other information relevant for PREP4BLUE		

Specific comments